

1 **SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND PERFORMANCE**
2 **EVALUATION OF SPINEL-DERIVED Ni/Al₂O₃ CATALYSTS FOR**
3 **VARIOUS METHANE REFORMING REACTIONS**

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21 **Abstract**

22 The catalytic performance of bulk nickel aluminate catalysts synthesised by co-
23 precipitation (NiAl₂O₄-CP) and co-dissolution (NiAl₂O₄-D) was examined for various
24 methane reforming reactions, namely partial oxidation, steam reforming and oxidative
25 steam reforming. The calcined and reduced spinels were thoroughly characterised by a
26 wide number of analytical techniques including WDXRF, N₂ physisorption, XRD, UV-
27 visible-NIR DRS, XPS, TEM, H₂-TPR and NH₃-TPD. The characterisation results of
28 the calcined samples at 850 °C showed that nickel aluminate phase was mainly obtained
29 on the NiAl₂O₄-CP near-surface together with a small NiO excess. By contrast, a large
30 amount of NiO phase was formed on NiAl₂O₄-D and deposited on the spinel surface.
31 The reduction at 850 °C of the two samples produced monodispersed Ni particles
32 (10.6 nm) in the NiAl₂O₄-CP while larger metallic nickel (17.7 nm) was deposited on
33 the NiAl₂O₄-D. In the three investigated reforming reactions the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst
34 proved to be highly active, stable and resistant toward carbon deposition. Moreover, the
35 performances of the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst appeared to be generally comparable with that
36 of a commercial 1%Rh/Al₂O₃ catalyst. The difference in catalytic behaviour between
37 the two nickel aluminates was related to the Ni dispersion, its particle size and its
38 capacity to minimize the acid character of the alumina by covering a large part of its
39 surface.

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44 *Keywords:* Nickel aluminate, Co-precipitation, Co-dissolution, Ni Crystallite size,
45 Methane reforming

46

47 **1. Introduction**

48 Methane steam reforming (SRM) is the most used technology for producing synthesis
49 gas (CO and H₂) from natural gas [1-5]. Moreover, this technology is a preferable
50 choice for producing clean and larger hydrogen yield. However, because of the high
51 cost of the endothermic character of SRM, the exothermic methane partial oxidation
52 (POM) appears as an alternative as it offers some interesting advantages especially
53 when the posterior use of the syngas stream requires a suitable H₂/CO ratio [6-8].
54 Currently industrial facilities are equipped with systems that offer the possibility of
55 using POM and/or SRM technologies. The combination of the POM and SRM strategies
56 called oxidative steam reforming (OSRM) has the advantage of controlling the process
57 heat and the distribution of the products by adjusting the O/C molar ratio [9-10].
58 Ni-based catalysts are widely used for methane reforming reactions due to their high
59 activity and their competitive costs compared to noble metals [11-13]. Alumina
60 supported Ni systems have particularly received considerable attention because of their
61 practical applications for a variety of reforming reactions [14-18]. Nevertheless, despite
62 exhibiting advantageous catalytic properties, alumina lacks an adequate thermal stability
63 which provokes the sintering of supported metals. Furthermore, the use of alumina as
64 support material has the drawback of rapid deactivation of the catalyst due to carbon
65 deposition on its active acid surface [19-20]. For this reason, the interest of recent
66 investigations has been focused on the preparation of formulations leading to a high
67 dispersion of Ni species which can cover alumina surface, thus minimising the negative
68 effect of its acid character. In this sense, the effect of the addition of some alkali and
69 alkali earth metals, used as chemical promoters, on the activity and stability of
70 Ni/alumina catalysts has been extensively investigated. Typically these additives help to

71 avoid carbon deposition and enhance their stability but at the expense of a reduction of
72 their activity due to the blocking of the more reactive Ni sites [21,22].

73 Within the same objective (the need to improve stability of Ni-based catalysts) nickel
74 aluminate synthesis is one of the routes proposed in the literature for the design of a
75 precursor capable to produce, after its reduction, metallic Ni presenting strong
76 interaction with alumina [14,15,23-25]. For so long, Ross et al. [25] had evidenced the
77 participation of the reduced surface nickel aluminate sites in the steam reforming of
78 methane over Ni/alumina catalysts. Since then, a number of studies dealing with the
79 preparation of nickel aluminate as precursor of active Ni metallic particles for methane
80 reforming reactions are available in the literature. A great majority of these works have
81 been devoted to the investigation of the influence of preparation methods on the
82 stability and the activity of the final formed Ni structures in reforming reactions
83 [14,15,24,26,27]. As stated in various references, it is however complicated to
84 synthesise pure or stoichiometric nickel aluminate by means of conventional methods of
85 synthesis. This is because of the formation of NiO as an excess even when heating at
86 very high temperatures (>1300 °C) [28-30]. Therefore, many works have examined the
87 impact of this particularity on the catalysts performance [15,16,24,27,31].

88 In our previous study, we compared two series of Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts with similar metal
89 content prepared by co-impregnation, using solutions containing a mixture of nickel
90 acetate and aluminium nitrate to obtain a stoichiometric NiAl₂O₄ supported on alumina,
91 and simple impregnation of nickel on alumina [15]. We demonstrated that, in methane
92 steam reforming, the co-impregnated catalyst was more active and we attributed this
93 behaviour to its higher Ni-support interaction. We also noticed that obtaining the active
94 metallic Ni, with small particle size, was controlled by the NiO/NiAl₂O₄ ratio initially
95 present in the calcined samples. Achouri et al. [16] also studied the influence of the

96 preparation method on the catalytic activity in diesel steam reforming of two alumina-
97 supported nickel aluminate catalysts prepared by wet-impregnation and co-precipitation.
98 They concluded that the impregnated catalyst exhibited a higher catalytic performance
99 and stability over time than the co-precipitated counterpart. This different behaviour
100 was explained by the higher carbon deposition tendency shown by the co-precipitated
101 sample.

102 In this paper the influence of the physico-chemical characteristics of two bulk nickel
103 aluminate catalysts, prepared by co-precipitation and co-dissolution methods, on their
104 catalytic behaviour in POM, SRM and OSRM reactions is investigated. To reach this
105 target, an extensive characterisation has been carried out by a wide number of analytical
106 techniques including BET measurements, XRD, XPS, UV-visible-NIR DRS, TEM and
107 H₂-TPR. Likewise, TPD of NH₃, a well-known probe molecule for acid sites, has been
108 used to characterise the surface chemistry of the investigated samples. A special
109 attention has been paid to the determination of the different nickel species formed after
110 high-temperature calcination and subsequent high-temperature reduction. In order to
111 examine and compare their catalytic efficiency the two prepared catalysts were
112 evaluated in partial oxidation, steam reforming and oxidative steam reforming of
113 methane. Interesting conclusions are drawn from the correlation between the
114 distribution of Ni active species of the two catalysts and their performance in these three
115 reforming reactions.

116

117 **2. Experimental**

118 **2.1. Catalysts preparation**

119 Bulk nickel aluminate samples were synthesised by co-precipitation (CP) and co-
120 dissolution (D) methods. The sample named NiAl₂O₄-D was synthesised using two

121 aqueous solutions of $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{-COO})_2\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3\cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Then they were mixed
122 (leading to a mixture with the desired 1:2 Ni/Al molar ratio), and evaporated on a hot
123 plate (150 °C). In the case of $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-CP}$, aqueous ammonia was added to the mixed
124 aqueous solutions to adjust the final suitable pH (=8). For comparative purposes NiO
125 was also prepared by simple calcination in air of $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{-COO})_2\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. All the samples
126 were dried at 110 °C overnight and then calcined at 850 °C in static air for 4 h at a
127 heating rate of 10 °C min^{-1} . Finally, pellets of bulk (nickel aluminate or nickel oxide)
128 samples were prepared by a process of compressing the powders into flakes in a
129 hydraulic press (Specac), crushing and sieving (0.3-0.5 mm).

130

131 **2.2. Catalyst characterisation**

132 The catalysts were characterised by N_2 physisorption at -196 °C, wavelength dispersive
133 X-ray fluorescence (WDXRF), X-ray diffraction (XRD), ultraviolet-visible-near
134 infrared diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy
135 (XPS), temperature programmed reduction with hydrogen ($\text{H}_2\text{-TPR}$) and temperature
136 programmed desorption of NH_3 ($\text{NH}_3\text{-TPD}$). The experimental details of each analytical
137 technique are described elsewhere [14,15]. Additionally, the morphology and particle
138 size distribution of the nickel particles was examined by transmission electron
139 microscopy (TEM). Prior to analysis, the samples were dispersed in absolute ethanol
140 ultrasonically for 30 min, and 10 cm^3 of each sample were then placed on flexible film
141 (Parafilm® M). Glow-discharged carbon-coated copper grids were inverted onto the
142 droplets of each sample. After incubation for 1 min at room temperature, the grids were
143 manually blotted with filter paper air-dried. Digitally recorded 2D images of each
144 solution were taken at room temperature at a nominal magnification of 80000 on a
145 Jeol JEM-1230 transmission electron microscope, with a LaB_6 filament as the source of

146 electrons and operated at 100 kV. Digital images were recorded on an Orius SC1000
147 cooled slow-scan CCD camera, 4008×2672 pixels (GATAN), obtaining a final pixel
148 size of 0.85 Å pixel⁻¹. The particle size distribution was obtained from the measurement
149 of at least 300 particles using ImageJ software, and the average diameter was calculated
150 by $d_M = \sum d_i \cdot n_i / \sum n_i$, where n_i is the number of the particles of diameter d_i .

151 On the other hand, the amount of carbonaceous deposits on the used catalyst was
152 determined by dynamic thermogravimetry using a Setaram Setsys Evolution apparatus
153 under atmospheric pressure coupled to a Pfeiffer Prisma mass spectrometer (TPO-MS).
154 The mass loss and the sample temperature were continuously recorded by a
155 computerised data acquisition system. Previously, the samples (20 mg) were dried from
156 room temperature to 150 °C. Then, the temperature was increased from 150 to 850 °C at
157 a constant heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹. The oxidant stream was 5% O₂/He (50 cm³ min⁻¹)
158 flowing downwards onto the cylindrical sample holder.

159

160 **2.3. Catalytic tests**

161 The three methane reforming reactions were studied in a bench-scale fixed-bed reactor
162 operated at atmospheric pressure. The reactor was made of stainless steel with an
163 internal diameter of 9 mm and a height of 305 mm. Prior to the reaction the catalyst
164 (0.125 g) was diluted with inert quartz (0.875 g, 1-1.25 mm). The catalyst bed was
165 maintained in the reactor on a quartz wool plug. The temperature was measured by a
166 thermocouple placed between the particles of the catalyst. Before the reaction the
167 NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts were reduced in situ with a mixture of 5% H₂/N₂
168 at 850 °C for 2 h. Likewise, a 1% Rh/Al₂O₃ (Alfa Aesar, 132 m² g⁻¹) commercial
169 catalyst was reduced at 700 °C and its activity was used for comparative purposes in the
170 three methane reforming reactions.

171 Three different feed gas mixtures balanced with N₂ (38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹) were used
172 in each reforming reaction as follows:

173 i) 10% CH₄ and 5% O₂ in POM reaction.

174 ii) 10% CH₄ and 30% H₂O in SRM reaction.

175 iii) 10% CH₄, 30% H₂O and 5% O₂ in OSRM reaction.

176 The runs were sequentially carried out by increasing and decreasing the reaction
177 temperature (450 °C-550 °C-650 °C-550 °C-450 °C) with an accumulated time online of
178 about 63 h. Catalytic activity, product yields and stability were recorded during 12.5 h
179 at each reaction temperature. Feed and effluent streams were analysed online by a
180 MicroGC (Agilent 3000) equipped with a TCD detector. Two columns, Molecular Sieve
181 5A and Plot U, were used in a series/bypass arrangement for the complete separation of
182 H₂, N₂, O₂, CH₄, CO and CO₂. A cold trap at the outlet of the reactor was used to
183 condense out any water from the product gas stream. On basis of the molar flow at the
184 inlet and outlet of the reactor, conversion and product yields were calculated, according
185 to the following equations:

186
$$X(CH_4), \% = \frac{F(CO_{out}) + F(CO_2_{out})}{F(CH_4_{in})} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

187
$$Y(H_2) = \frac{F(H_2_{out})}{2 \cdot F(CH_4_{in})} \quad (2)$$

188
$$Y(CO) = \frac{F(CO_{out})}{F(CH_4_{in})} \quad (3)$$

189
$$Y(CO_2) = \frac{F(CO_2_{out})}{F(CH_4_{in})} \quad (4)$$

190 The thermodynamic data were calculated via the HSC Chemistry software package by
191 the GIBBS program using the so-called Gibbs Energy Minimization Method. For these
192 calculations, only enthalpy, entropy and heat capacity data for all prevailing compounds

193 were needed. The software calculated the amounts of products at equilibrium under
194 isothermal and isobaric conditions. The substances to be taken into account in the
195 calculations, the amount of reactants, the potentially stable phases as well as the
196 temperature of raw species were specified as input. In addition to solid carbon, the
197 following substances in the gas phase were considered: CH₄, O₂, N₂, CO, CO₂, H₂ and
198 H₂O. Calculations were performed in the 450-650 °C temperature range at atmospheric
199 pressure. Hence, the GIBBS program found the most stable phase combination and
200 determined the phase composition where the Gibbs energy for the system reached its
201 minimum at constant pressure and temperature.

202

203 **3. Results and discussions**

204 **3.1 Characterisation of the samples**

205 **3.1.1. N₂-physorption (BET measurements)**

206 N₂ adsorption at -196 °C on NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP showed that the isotherms (not
207 shown) were characteristic of mesoporous solids of type IV according to the IUPAC
208 classification. In the case of NiAl₂O₄-D the nitrogen desorption gave rise to a hysteresis
209 loop, H2 type, which was characteristic of disordered porous materials. Table 1 lists the
210 data obtained from the analysis of the textural properties of the calcined and reduced
211 samples. The prepared NiAl₂O₄-CP spinel (76 m² g⁻¹) had a higher surface area than
212 NiAl₂O₄-D (55 m² g⁻¹). This difference probably resulted from the preparation method
213 and the corresponding proportion of NiO formed in each sample, which will be
214 discussed in the XRD, H₂-TPR and XPS sections. Fig. 1 shows the pore sizes
215 distribution for the NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts. The pore size distribution
216 trace for the NiAl₂O₄-D sample exhibited one maximum at 7 nm in the low mesoporous
217 range (<10 nm) whereas the NiAl₂O₄-CP samples exhibited a peak centred at 20 nm.

218 After reduction at high temperature (850 °C) both samples decreased their total surface
219 area ($48 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for NiAl₂O₄-D and $55 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ for NiAl₂O₄-CP); however it did not
220 influence considerably their pore size distribution. A similar observation in line with the
221 decrease of specific surface area by the reduction process was previously reported in
222 various works dealing with Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts and multiple explanations have been
223 given to describe its origin [23,32]. For instance, Bartholomew et al. [32] reported that
224 the phase transformations and/or dispersed nickel can accelerate the loss of alumina
225 surface area in Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts.

226 Table 1/Fig. 1

227 3.1.2. X-ray diffraction (XRD)

228 The general formula of stoichiometric nickel aluminates (spinel structure) is NiAl₂O₄. It
229 crystallizes in the cubic system and belongs to Fd-3m space group [33-37]. Typically,
230 the framework of the “normal” spinel structures consists of an ensemble of tetrahedral
231 and octahedral coordination occupied by bivalent (Ni²⁺) and trivalent (Al³⁺) cations,
232 respectively [33,34]. However, this distribution can change when the Ni²⁺ partially
233 adopts the octahedral site while the tetrahedral site hosts the Al³⁺ together with Ni²⁺
234 ions. This structural flexibility generates a family of compounds of inverse spinel
235 structure described as Ni_{1-x}Al_x[Ni_xAl_{2-x}]O₄ ($0 < x < 1$) [33-37].

236 The NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP samples were characterized by means of X-ray powder
237 diffraction in order to investigate their structural properties. Fig. 2 compares the
238 diffractograms of the catalysts before and after reduction at 850 °C. The patterns of the
239 calcined NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP revealed the formation of the spinel structure
240 (JCPDS 78-1601). Furthermore, in the case of NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst additional peaks
241 associated with NiO structure, at 43.5° and 63.1°, were observed whereas the
242 diffractogram of NiAl₂O₄-CP showed no lines of NiO. A more careful analysis of the

243 pattern of NiAl₂O₄-D evidenced that the intensity ratio of the peaks corresponding to
244 (220) and (440) reticular planes differed from that of NiAl₂O₄-CP. This difference could
245 be explained by the cation distribution in the octahedral and tetrahedral sites affecting
246 the inversion degree of the spinel structure. The diffraction lines associated with the
247 (220) plane are related to the tetrahedrally-coordinated cations while the diffraction
248 signals belonging to the (440) plane are attributed to both tetrahedrally and
249 octahedrally-coordinated cations [35-37]. From our experimental data I(220)/I(440)
250 ratios were estimated. For the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst this ratio was 0.22, whereas it
251 increased up to 0.33 for the NiAl₂O₄-D. The increase in I(220)/I(440) ratio was also
252 observed by Wang et al. [36] in XRD patterns of various inverse spinel structures. This
253 feature was assigned to the increasing occupancy of the heavier cations on the
254 tetrahedral sites. We might accordingly conclude that on the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst nickel
255 was preferentially hosted in tetrahedral sites of the inverse spinel whereas nickel tended
256 to occupy the octahedral coordination in the case of NiAl₂O₄-CP sample prepared by
257 co-precipitation.

258 Fig. 2 also includes the X-ray diffraction patterns of the bulk nickel aluminates reduced
259 at 850 °C. A comparison of the NiAl₂O₄-CP patterns before and after reduction
260 confirmed that the transformation of Ni²⁺ ions of the spinel framework into metallic Ni
261 (JCPDS 89-7128) was complete. Likewise, the formation of alumina structure (JCPDS
262 79-1558) instead of the characteristic peaks attributed to spinel structure was noted.
263 However, in the case of the NiAl₂O₄-D sample, diffraction peaks with a low intensity
264 attributed to NiO were also observed. This could be reasonably explained by the surface
265 room temperature passivation of the catalyst [31]. Table 1 reports the metallic Ni
266 crystallite size, calculated by Scherrer equation, by using Ni (200) (2θ = 51.6°)
267 diffraction line broadening. The average size of Ni particles was found to be around

268 11 nm on the reduced NiAl₂O₄-CP while larger particles with an average size of about
269 23 nm were detected for the reduced NiAl₂O₄-D.

270 In sum, the obtained XRD results indicated that the preparation method of nickel
271 aluminate had an important effect on the excess of NiO and the Ni²⁺ ions distribution,
272 between tetrahedral and octahedral sites in the spinel structure. Moreover, the reduction
273 of the NiAl₂O₄-CP sample prepared by co-precipitation method produced smaller Ni
274 particles in comparison with the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst.

275 Fig. 2

276 3.1.3. Temperature programmed reduction (H₂-TPR)

277 The TPR experiments were performed in order to determine the different Ni reducible
278 species present in the two prepared spinel catalysts (Fig. 3). The H₂-TPR profiles
279 included in Fig. 3 suggested the full reduction of the spinel catalysts (NiAl₂O₄-D and
280 NiAl₂O₄-CP) with an overall H₂ uptake close to the theoretical value 5.7 mmol H₂ g⁻¹
281 (within the experimental error) (Table 2). It was observed, however, that the shape of
282 the TPR traces depended on the preparation method. The thermogram of the NiAl₂O₄-D
283 sample displayed a typical reduction spectrum of a mixture of two Ni species consisting
284 of free NiO (α -peak at 400 °C) and nickel aluminates structures (β -peak at 600 °C and
285 γ -peak at 800 °C) [14-15]. In the case of NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst it was noted that the
286 characteristic reduction peak attributed to bulk NiO (at 400 °C) was absent. The
287 observed three H₂ uptakes in the profile of the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst were located at 520,
288 750 and 825 °C. The peak at 520 °C was attributed to the highly dispersed NiO.
289 Generally, the NiO reduction peak shifts towards high temperatures, as in the case of
290 NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst, when the NiO particles strongly interact with the support [31].
291 Above 600 °C, the high-temperature reduction peaks at 750 and 825 °C were due to the
292 reduction of Ni²⁺ ions incorporated in the nickel aluminate structure. The relative

293 abundance of the NiO species in the NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP samples was estimated
294 to be 33% and 9%, respectively (Table 2). Since the specific surface area of the bulk
295 NiO was very low ($< 1 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$), the relative abundance of the NiO in each sample could
296 explain the difference observed in the specific surface area. Note that the XRD pattern
297 of the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst showed that no peaks due to NiO were observed probably
298 because of its low amount and/or its high dispersion.

299 Table 2/Fig. 3

300 Though it was reported that free NiO present on the spinel reduces at low temperature
301 and favours the reduction of nickel located in the spinel [24], to our knowledge, the real
302 origin of the splitting of the nickel aluminates peak reduction has never been discussed.
303 As deduced from our XRD study, on the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst, nickel mainly has a
304 tetrahedral coordination whereas it was mainly octahedrally coordinated in the case of
305 NiAl₂O₄-CP. We believe that the two observed reduction peaks and their position could
306 be related to the different Ni²⁺ coordination in the spinel framework. Furthermore, since
307 the contribution of the β -peak in the total Ni species present in the spinel structure of
308 NiAl₂O₄-D was lower (27%) than that of NiAl₂O₄-CP (51%), it could be concluded that
309 Ni²⁺ ions occupying octahedral sites were more prone to be reduced than the tetrahedral
310 ones.

311 **3.1.4. UV–visible–NIR diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS)**

312 The coordination and the oxidation state of nickel species on the NiAl₂O₄-D and
313 NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts were studied by means of diffuse reflectance spectroscopy. Fig. 4
314 showed the UV-visible-NIR spectra of the two prepared samples and the spectrum of
315 pure NiO presented as reference. The shape of NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D spectra
316 resulted almost identical. All the spectra displayed a strong absorption in the UV
317 domain. The maxima centred at 220-345 nm were ascribed to $\text{O}^{2-} \rightarrow \text{Ni}^{2+}$ metal to

318 ligand charge transfers [14,15,38]. In the visible range, the bands located at 380 nm and
319 720 nm were associated with ν_3 (${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$) and ν_2 (${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$) absorptions that
320 resulted from d-d transitions of Ni^{2+} ions hosted by octahedral sites [14,15,38,39]. The
321 spectra were also characterised by the presence of an additional intense band in the
322 range of 600–645 nm and shoulders at 550 nm and 760 nm, assigned to the
323 (${}^3T_1(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$) ligand transitions, thereby evidencing the presence of the
324 tetrahedrally coordinated Ni^{2+} ions.

325 In the NIR a broad resolved band located around 1130 nm was observed which was
326 ascribed to the ν_1 (${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$) transition of Ni^{2+} in octahedral symmetry [14,15,38,39].
327 Comparing the intensity of this absorption band it was clear that the relative abundance
328 of octahedral Ni^{2+} ions in $NiAl_2O_4$ -CP was superior to that of $NiAl_2O_4$ -D. This was in
329 accordance with the results obtained by XRD. However, the quantification of tetrahedral
330 Ni^{2+} ions on the spectra was difficult because of the overlapping of the absorption
331 domains of Ni^{2+} ions in tetrahedral and octahedral symmetries.

332 On the other hand, it should be pointed out that the spectrum of $NiAl_2O_4$ -D exhibited
333 two additional shoulders: (i) the first one was located around 420 nm, (ii) the second
334 one at a wavelength of 450 nm. Since the presence of these bands was also detected in
335 the spectrum of NiO, they could be assigned to d–d transitions caused by the ligand
336 field of unsupported NiO. These bands were expectedly absent from the spectrum of
337 $NiAl_2O_4$ -CP, thus confirming that NiO was exclusively formed on the calcined
338 $NiAl_2O_4$ -D. These results suggested, in line with XRD characterisation, that in contrast
339 to $NiAl_2O_4$ -CP, the preparation of $NiAl_2O_4$ -D led to the formation of nickel aluminate
340 together with NiO structure. Furthermore, these evidences could reasonably explain the
341 greenish-blue colour of the $NiAl_2O_4$ -D sample and the dark blue colour of $NiAl_2O_4$ -CP.

342 Fig. 4

343 **3.1.5. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)**

344 The chemical composition and the distribution of nickel species laying on the surface of
345 the calcined NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D catalysts were investigated by means of XPS
346 measurements. The Ni 2p_{3/2} and O 1s photoemission peaks for the two analysed samples
347 were shown in Fig. 5. The different broadness and the symmetry of the Ni 2p_{3/2} and O 1s
348 main peaks for NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D oxides were evident. As revealed by the
349 analysis of the spectra included in Fig. 5 the NiAl₂O₄-D sample showed much broader
350 and less symmetric peaks, thus suggesting a larger heterogeneity in its nickel
351 environments. On the basis of these observations the Ni 2p_{3/2} and O 1s spectra of
352 NiAl₂O₄-D were deconvoluted. As a result, the main Ni 2p_{3/2} XPS peak displayed two
353 bands. The first one located at 854.1 eV was associated with NiO exhibiting weak
354 interaction NiO-NiAl₂O₄ [15]. The second one, centred at 856.8 eV, was related to
355 Ni²⁺ ions in the network of nickel aluminates [15]. On the other hand, the O 1s signal of
356 the NiAl₂O₄-D XPS spectrum could be decomposed into three components: the first one
357 at 528.5 eV assigned to O²⁻ in NiO, the second situated at 531.1 eV due to NiAl₂O₄
358 phase and the third one located at high binding energies 532.6 eV characteristic of pure
359 Al₂O₃ [15]. By contrast, because of their apparent symmetry the O 1s and Ni 2p_{3/2}
360 signals of NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst suggested the presence of a unique phase. The
361 comparison of the positions of the O 1s (530.6 eV) and Ni 2p_{3/2} (855.7 eV) peaks with
362 the attributions mentioned above revealed that the NiAl₂O₄-CP near-surface was mainly
363 composed of nickel aluminate structure. Note that despite of the fact that the occurrence
364 of the small fraction of NiO phase was detected for this sample by H₂-TPR, its XPS
365 spectra did not reveal the presence of this species. This might be explained by the strong
366 interaction of the highly dispersed NiO with NiAl₂O₄ phase that was reflected by the
367 shifting of its XPS peak towards higher binding energy.

Fig. 5

368
369 The difference in Ni/Al atomic ratio determined by XPS between NiAl₂O₄-CP and
370 NiAl₂O₄-D also supported our conclusion about the structural composition of near-
371 surface. According to Table 2, the Ni/Al atomic ratio of NiAl₂O₄-CP (0.6) was smaller
372 than that determined for NiAl₂O₄-D (1), suggesting that the surface of the co-
373 precipitated sample was comparatively deficient in nickel. Thus, in view of the
374 stoichiometry of the pure spinel (Ni/Al=0.5), it could be concluded that nickel
375 aluminate phase was mainly obtained on the NiAl₂O₄-CP near-surface together with a
376 small NiO excess. A larger amount of NiO phase was however formed on NiAl₂O₄-D.

377 **3.1.6. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)**

378 NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D samples, reduced at 850 °C, were investigated by
379 transmission electron microscopy as well. Fig. 6(a) and 6(b) show the TEM
380 micrographs and size distribution diagrams (obtained from the measurement of about
381 300 particles). The micrographs of both samples showed no significant differences in
382 morphology. In both cases spherical particles of nickel were observed. Nevertheless, it
383 was visualised that nickel was homogeneously dispersed in NiAl₂O₄-CP while it was
384 much more heterogeneous on the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst. The particle size distribution in
385 the co-precipitated sample presented a unimodal shape with an average size of 10.6 nm
386 (dispersion of 9.5%). By contrast a broad distribution ranging from 10 to 50 nm was
387 obtained for the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst with a corresponding average size of 17.7 nm
388 (dispersion of 4%). By correlating the Ni particle size distributions with the results of
389 H₂-TPR, XRD, XPS and UV-visible-NIR DRS it could be reasonably assumed that the
390 smaller mono-dispersed particles present on the NiAl₂O₄-CP corresponded to particles
391 resulted from the reduction of nickel aluminate phase whereas the range of larger
392 particles deposited on the NiAl₂O₄-D was originated by the reduction of the free NiO.

393 As stated previously, the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst contained two Ni species as a mixture of
394 free NiO and nickel aluminate phase while NiAl₂O₄-CP was composed mainly by nickel
395 aluminate together with a relatively small fraction of highly dispersed NiO (as proved
396 by H₂-TPR). Furthermore, we thought that the difference between NiAl₂O₄-D and
397 NiAl₂O₄-CP probably resulted from the textural properties of each catalyst as well. The
398 NiAl₂O₄-D average pore size was smaller (7.5 nm) compared to its Ni particles average
399 size, suggesting that nickel was mainly deposited on the external surface. However, the
400 NiAl₂O₄-CP average pore size was around 15 nm and this might limit the growth of the
401 Ni crystallites during the reduction.

402 Fig. 6

403 **3.1.7. Temperature programmed desorption of NH₃ (NH₃-TPD)**

404 The surface acidity of the two catalysts was characterised by means of temperature
405 programmed desorption, using ammonia as probe molecule, followed by dynamic
406 thermogravimetry and coupled to a mass spectrometer [15]. The overall acidity of the
407 samples (calcined and reduced spinel catalysts) was quantified from the net weight gain
408 during the adsorption step at 100 °C followed by the removal of physically bound
409 ammonia from the surface with flowing helium.

410 The deconvolution of the NH₃-TPD thermograms of the calcined NiAl₂O₄-D and
411 NiAl₂O₄-CP samples exhibited two bands corresponding to two types of acid sites
412 (Fig. 7). The first one consisted of a peak located at low temperatures (<220 °C)
413 accompanied by a second much more intense feature at relatively high temperatures
414 (250-370 °C), the latter being probably due to a fraction of strong acid sites present at
415 the surface of the catalysts. It must be pointed out that, in the case of the two reduced
416 samples, the MS analysis of the exit stream revealed the presence of trace amounts of
417 N₂ and H₂ related to the decomposition of the probe molecule on the reduced sites.

418 The obtained quantitative results were summarised in Table 1. It was found that the
419 surface density of NH_3 adsorbed on the calcined $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-CP}$, $3.82 \mu\text{mol NH}_3 \text{ m}^{-2}$, was
420 smaller than that determined for the calcined $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-D}$, $4.95 \mu\text{mol NH}_3 \text{ m}^{-2}$. The
421 difference could be related to the structural composition of each catalyst. As
422 demonstrated by XPS analysis the $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-D}$ catalyst contained alumina phase in its
423 near-surface which could improve its surface acid properties. It should be pointed out
424 that the H_2 reduction at $850 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ of the two catalysts appeared to increase both the amount
425 and the thermal stability of the adsorbed NH_3 by shifting the desorption peaks towards
426 higher temperatures. The acid surface density for reduced $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-CP}$ was estimated to
427 reach $4.38 \mu\text{mol NH}_3 \text{ m}^{-2}$ in comparison with $5.7 \mu\text{mol NH}_3 \text{ m}^{-2}$ for $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-D}$
428 (Table 1). These results might be related to the formation of alumina instead of nickel
429 aluminate structure in the two reduced samples, as proved by XRD analysis. In addition,
430 the presence of homogeneous and highly dispersed nickel in the reduced $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-CP}$
431 catalyst, as confirmed by TEM analysis, could explain the occurrence of a small fraction
432 of surface acid sites in comparison with $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-D}$. By contrast, the low Ni dispersion
433 (4%) on the latter led to a large uncovered acid support surface.

434 Fig. 7

435

436 **3.2. Catalytic activity**

437 **3.2.1 Partial oxidation of methane (POM)**

438 The POM reaction was carried out on the activated (calcination followed by reduction)
439 $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-CP}$, $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-D}$ and 1% $\text{Rh/Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (used as reference) catalysts, at 450, 550 and
440 $650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, by sequentially increasing the reaction temperature with $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ intervals. The
441 inverse sequence was conducted by decreasing the reaction temperature (from 650 to
442 550 and $450 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) in order to probe the stability of the catalysts. Fig. 8 shows the obtained

443 results in terms of CH₄ conversion and H₂, CO and CO₂ yields. The corresponding
444 equilibrium data are included as well (calculated via the HSC Chemistry software
445 package by the GIBBS program using the so-called Gibbs Energy Minimization
446 Method). The reported data evidenced that the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst was typically more
447 active than the NiAl₂O₄-D. Furthermore, over the co-precipitated sample methane
448 conversion as well as H₂, CO and CO₂ yields were fairly stable during 12.5 h on stream
449 (Fig. 9). At 450 °C the conversion on this sample was around 25% and it increased to
450 reach about 36% at 550 °C and 58% at 650 °C. Likewise, the increase in the reaction
451 temperature promoted the H₂ yield, which attained 0.56. Carbon monoxide production
452 also increased up to 0.44 at 650 °C. It is noteworthy that at 650 °C both conversion and
453 yields achieved with NiAl₂O₄-CP were close to the values obtained with the commercial
454 1%Rh/Al₂O₃ catalyst. As the performance of the noble metal-based catalyst is
455 considered as reference in the POM reaction [40-43], these catalytic features evidenced
456 the potential of NiAl₂O₄-CP as a promising alternative catalyst. By contrast, the activity
457 appeared to decrease with time on stream in the case of NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst. It was
458 thought that this difference in the catalytic activity between the two reduced spinel
459 catalysts was related to the Ni particle size. Indeed, our TEM results showed that on the
460 NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst metallic nickel was deposited with a smaller size (10.6 nm)
461 compared to the NiAl₂O₄-D (17.7 nm).

462 As shown in Fig. 9, methane conversion at 450 °C gradually decreased from 29% at the
463 beginning of the reaction to 25% after 12.5 h on stream. Likewise, H₂, CO and CO₂
464 yields were not stable with time on line. Indeed, a slight increase in activity followed by
465 a stable plateau was observed when the reaction temperature decreased which could be
466 a result of an excess of carbon formation (Fig. 9).

467 Table 3 lists the H₂/CO and CO/CO₂ ratios calculated for each reaction temperature on
468 the tested catalysts. Note that, on the two tested nickel catalysts, the CO/CO₂ ratio
469 seemed to increase with reaction temperature. For instance, at 450 °C the CO/CO₂ ratio
470 on the NiAl₂O₄-CP was around 0.1 and it increased to reach about 3 at 650 °C. At low
471 CO/CO₂ values (corresponding to relatively low temperatures) CO disproportionation
472 and/or methane total oxidation reaction may occur producing CO₂ and carbon and/or
473 H₂O. On the other hand, the H₂/CO ratio was in all the cases higher than 2 (ranging
474 between 2.2 and 2.5). It is widely accepted that the encapsulation of the metal particles
475 by deposited carbon does not occur if H₂/CO or H₂O/hydrocarbon ratios are sufficiently
476 high [32]. Accordingly, our results showed, by comparing the NiAl₂O₄-CP and
477 NiAl₂O₄-D catalysts, that the catalyst with the highest H₂/CO ratio (NiAl₂O₄-CP) did
478 not suffer apparent deactivation.

479 Fig. 8/Fig. 9/Table 3

480 Thermogravimetric (not shown) and TPO-MS analyses (Fig. 10) performed in order to
481 determine the amount of carbon accumulated on the used catalysts in POM resulted in
482 deposited carbon masses of 2.4 wt.% on NiAl₂O₄-CP (close to 2 wt% observed for the
483 commercial rhodium catalyst) and 46.5 wt.% on NiAl₂O₄-D (Table 3). Both TPO traces
484 consisted of a CO₂ production major peak at approximately 670 °C (Fig. 10). Thus, the
485 same type of carbonaceous species was present on the two catalysts. It could be
486 concluded, therefore, that the deactivation of NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst might mainly occur as
487 a result of the substantial formation of coke. This was in agreement with XRD analysis
488 of the spent catalysts which confirmed the formation of carbon (graphite) on the two
489 catalysts. Specially, it was observed that the principal peak (26.4°) was much more
490 intense in the NiAl₂O₄-D diffractogram than that of NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst (Fig. 2). On
491 the other hand, the Ni (200) (2θ = 51.6°) diffraction line broadening was used to

492 estimate, by Scherrer equation, the evolution of metallic Ni crystallite size after catalytic
493 test (Table 1). It was found that the growth of Ni⁰ crystallites during POM reaction on
494 NiAl₂O₄-D for extended periods of time was significant (size estimated to be around
495 23 nm in the reduced sample while it was around 35 nm after catalytic test). In
496 agreement with a previous study which reported that, in the methane reforming
497 reactions, the larger Ni crystallites on the Ni catalyst favoured the formation of graphitic
498 carbon [44], we could conclude that the same phenomenon occurred in the case of our
499 NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst. As stated previously, the reduction of the Ni species deposited on
500 this sample produced large metallic Ni which was less resistant to sintering and coke
501 formation.

502 Fig. 10

503 The XRD diffractograms of the spent nickel aluminate catalysts also evidenced the
504 presence of NiO phase (Fig. 2). The NiO characteristic peaks were much more intense
505 on the NiAl₂O₄-CP diffractogram suggesting that the oxidation of Ni species during the
506 POM reaction was influenced by their interaction with the support. Accordingly, it
507 seemed that the oxidation of the smaller Ni particles, during POM reaction, might be
508 easier. Indeed, our H₂-TPR and TEM studies indicated that more than two distinct
509 metallic nickel populations were present on NiAl₂O₄-D in contrast with the NiAl₂O₄-CP
510 catalyst with a narrower and more homogeneous size distribution (size = 10.6 nm). In
511 their study on the mechanism for POM reaction, Jin et al. [45] claimed that during the
512 CH₄/O₂ reaction over Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts, Ni⁰ was first oxidised to NiO, and the latter
513 was reduced again by CH₄ during the transient process. Since the reduction of NiO by
514 CH₄ is endothermic and as the last step of our catalytic experiments occurred at 450 °C
515 (relatively low temperature) the presence of the characteristic peaks of NiO in our XRD
516 diffractograms of the used samples could be justified. Furthermore, the presence of the

517 NiO could explain the low CO/CO₂ ratios obtained at low temperatures suggesting that
518 this gave rise to total oxidation instead of reforming reaction.

519 On the other hand, as described in previous works the carbon deposition may deactivate
520 the catalyst either by covering of the active sites and/or by pore blocking [32,44-46]. In
521 our case, it was found that, after catalytic tests, the pore size distribution of NiAl₂O₄-D
522 catalyst shifted towards higher values (8.1 nm to 10.7 nm) suggesting the blocking of
523 the pores with small sizes by carbon deposition (Table 1). In addition, it should be noted
524 that carbon deposition on the NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D catalysts appeared to
525 significantly increase the surface area (Table 1). Thus, on NiAl₂O₄-D the specific
526 surface area increased from 48 to 57 m² g⁻¹ whereas over NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst it
527 increased from 55 to 64 m² g⁻¹, suggesting that this might be due to the similar porous
528 nature of the carbon deposited on the two catalysts [46].

529 On the other hand, the chemical properties of their near surface could have an effect on
530 the catalytic activity and stability of NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts. Generally,
531 acidity is considered to induce a negative impact on methane reforming behaviour by
532 catalysing the coke formation [32]. In agreement with our NH₃-TPD studies, the surface
533 of NiAl₂O₄-D bears more acid sites than that of NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst. This difference in
534 the acid character could explain the markedly larger formation of coke on the surface of
535 the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst in comparison with NiAl₂O₄-CP.

536 In addition, the inversion degree of the formed spinel was another factor to take into
537 consideration in order to explain the different performances of NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-
538 CP in POM reaction. In their study on the methane dry reforming reaction over nickel
539 aluminate catalysts Kathiraser et al. [26] concluded that the inverse NiAl₂O₄ spinel
540 structure positively affected the catalytic activity compared to the normal spinel. Our
541 characterization results showed that NiAl₂O₄-CP tended to be in the inverse

542 coordination while the NiAl₂O₄-D was close to the normal spinel phase. The observed
543 divergence between NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP might influence the catalytic
544 behaviour of these catalysts as well.

545 **3.2.2. Steam reforming of methane (SRM)**

546 Fig. 8 show CH₄ conversion and H₂, CO and CO₂ yields in the SRM reaction for the
547 examined reduced catalysts as function of temperature. In all cases methane conversion
548 as well as H₂, CO and CO₂ yields were stable with time on stream. Moreover, the
549 NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D catalysts were markedly more active than
550 1%Rh/Al₂O₃ (80% and 53% vs. 46% at 650 °C, respectively). The comparison of the
551 performance of the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst in POM and SRM reactions showed that
552 replacing oxygen with steam resulted in poorer methane conversion and CO yield while
553 it improved the H₂ production. By contrast, when compared to its performance in POM
554 reaction, an increase in activity as well as CO and H₂ yields were observed over
555 NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst in SRM reaction, especially at 550 °C and 650 °C. Furthermore,
556 among the three catalysts the best methane conversion and the largest H₂, CO and CO₂
557 yields were achieved with NiAl₂O₄-CP at the three reaction temperatures. Thus, at
558 450 °C the NiAl₂O₄-D and 1%Rh/Al₂O₃ catalysts exhibited a poor performance as their
559 activity did not exceed 10% (the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst gave a conversion of 21% at this
560 temperature). It should be noted that the CO production, at 450 °C, was very low or
561 negligible over the three tested catalysts. However, considerable yields of CO₂ (0.18
562 over NiAl₂O₄-CP and 0.07 over NiAl₂O₄-D) and H₂ (0.5 over NiAl₂O₄-CP and 0.22
563 over NiAl₂O₄-D) were obtained suggesting the main occurrence of water gas shift
564 reaction. On the effect of the SRM reaction temperature on the catalytic performance of
565 the Ni catalysts, we noted that higher temperatures improved conversion which rapidly
566 increased to reach about 80% and 53% over NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D respectively

567 (at 650 °C). Likewise, irrespective of the used catalyst both H₂ and CO yields increased
568 as the SRM reaction temperature increased. This trend was more pronounced on the
569 NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst which led to CO (0.47 at 650 °C) and H₂ (1.6 at 650 °C) yields and
570 a H₂/CO ratio close to the thermodynamic equilibrium.

571 On the other hand, as expected, the activity of the three catalysts was not accompanied
572 by the carbon deposition (Table 3) which might be explained by adding water to the
573 feed with a high H₂O/CH₄ ratio (around 3). The observed H₂/CO ratio was in all the
574 cases higher than 6. As no significant carbon deposition was detected (Table 3), one
575 could conclude that this was the reason for the stability of the NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-
576 CP tested catalysts. Note that, for both NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts, no
577 significant loss of their surface area was observed. XRD patterns of the NiAl₂O₄-D and
578 NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts recorded after the tests did not show any noticeable difference
579 when compared with that of the freshly reduced samples suggesting that they did not
580 undergo any noticeable alteration of their crystalline structures during the reaction
581 (Fig. 2). However, an appreciable increase of Ni particle size was noticed in the case of
582 NiAl₂O₄-D. Since this did not affect its catalytic stability the Ni particles growth was
583 supposed to rapidly occur at the start of the reaction. Note that, while the stable catalytic
584 behaviour could be eventually masked by mass transfer limitations at 650 °C, the fact is
585 that a good stability was also noticed at lower temperatures (450 and 550 °C). In
586 principle, the contribution of mass transfer limitations to the observed catalytic
587 performance could be considered negligible under these conditions. In sum, it seems
588 that the experimentally reforming behaviour of the NiAl₂O₄-D actually was that of a
589 reduced spinel catalyst with a crystallite size of 47 nm (instead of 23 nm). This
590 behaviour could be related with the nature of the Ni species deposited and their
591 interactions with the carrier. Our characterisation results showed that the difference

592 between the two NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D catalysts was related to the fact that the
593 reduction of the Ni species produced monodispersed fixed nickel on the first one
594 whereas it produced larger particles of free nickel on the second one. On the effect of
595 this distribution we could conclude, then, that the growth of Ni particles in SRM
596 reaction, observed exclusively on NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst, concerned only the free deposited
597 metallic Ni.

598 **3.2.3. Oxidative steam reforming of methane (OSRM)**

599 Finally the catalytic performance in OSRM reaction was also studied and the results are
600 collected in Fig. 8. At the three investigated reaction temperatures the best methane
601 conversion and the largest H₂ and CO yields, over the Ni catalysts, were achieved with
602 the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst. Moreover, compared to its behaviour in POM reaction, a
603 significant improvement of the catalytic activity could be noted; especially at 450 °C
604 and 550 °C reaction temperatures where it was even more active than the 1%Rh/Al₂O₃
605 catalyst. By contrast, the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst clearly gave the lowest methane
606 conversion. Furthermore, the BET surface area of this sample decreased from 48 to
607 37 m² g⁻¹ after reaction. Nevertheless, the water addition to the feed significantly
608 improved the catalytic stability of NiAl₂O₄-D with respect to the POM reaction. Indeed,
609 the literature reported that the excess of water or oxygen to the feed cleans the metallic
610 surface and improve the stability of the catalyst [47]. Accordingly, our estimation of
611 deposited coke, by thermogravimetric and TPO-MS analysis, was less than 1%wt. on
612 both NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts. On the other hand, the combination of POM
613 and SRM gas mixtures seemed to increase the CO₂ yield, which attained 0.41 on the
614 NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst at 650 °C. Moreover, CO/CO₂ ratio did not exceed 0.5, which
615 could be explained by a high combustion activity and a low reforming activity [10].

616 Fig. 2 also shows the XRD patterns of the NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts used in
617 OSRM reaction. The absence of 26.4° diffraction peak indicated that, on both catalysts,
618 no graphite carbon deposition occurred during the tests. By contrast, changes in the Ni
619 crystallite size were noted. For the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst the Ni particle size increased
620 from 22 up to 29 nm, whereas for the NiAl₂O₄-CP it decreased from 11 to 7 nm
621 (Table 1). Similar changes were observed on the XRD patterns of the latter in POM
622 reaction suggesting that a re-distribution of Ni active phases might have occurred which
623 favoured its activity and stability. However, on the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst this re-
624 distribution (increased Ni particle size) provoked the decay of its activity. The XRD
625 diffractograms of the used NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts in OSRM reaction also
626 showed the presence of intense diffraction peaks attributed to the NiO phase (Fig. 2). A
627 similar behaviour was reported by Yoshida et al. [10] in their study of OSR reaction
628 over Ni/ α -Al₂O₃ and they explained it by the oxidation of the Ni species in the presence
629 of gas-phase oxygen. The formation of these Ni oxidised species could explain the high
630 activity of our Ni catalysts for methane combustion.

631

632 **4. Conclusions**

633 The behaviour of two bulk nickel aluminate (NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D) has been
634 investigated in the partial oxidation, steam reforming and oxidative steam reforming of
635 methane. These catalysts have been prepared by co-precipitation and co-dissolution
636 methods, respectively, and characterised by N₂ physisorption, XRD, UV–visible–NIR
637 DRS, XPS, TEM, H₂-TPR and NH₃-TPD.

638 XRD, H₂-TPR, UV–visible spectroscopy and XPS analyses show that the two catalysts,
639 calcined at 850 °C, contain nickel aluminate as a major phase together with NiO which
640 was considered as an excess. Moreover, it has been proved that on the NiAl₂O₄-D

641 catalyst nickel is preferentially hosted in tetrahedral sites of the inverse spinel whereas it
642 tends to occupy the octahedral coordination in the case of NiAl₂O₄-CP sample. As
643 showed by H₂-TPR, the interaction of the resulted NiO excess with the nickel aluminate
644 seems to depend on the preparation method. Indeed, the reduction of this NiO excess on
645 the NiAl₂O₄-D occurs at lower temperatures compared to the NiAl₂O₄-CP suggesting
646 that on the latter NiO has a strong interaction with nickel aluminate. TEM results
647 indicate that on the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst the reduction of the Ni species at 850 °C
648 produces homogeneous and monodispersed fixed nickel whereas heterogeneous and
649 larger metallic free nickel is detected on the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst. In addition, this
650 distribution has a marked effect on the chemical properties of the reduced catalysts
651 since the surface of reduced NiAl₂O₄-D contains more acid sites than that of reduced
652 NiAl₂O₄-CP.

653 A clearly different behaviour in the reforming of methane has been observed over the
654 NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D catalysts with same Ni composition but prepared by two
655 different methods. The results show that the reforming efficiency is highly dependent on
656 the type of interaction of the Ni active phase with the carrier. In the three tested
657 reforming reactions the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst, prepared by co-precipitation method, has
658 proved to be highly active and stable. However, as a result of the carbon deposition
659 found in POM reaction, methane conversion, H₂, CO and CO₂ yields are not stable with
660 time over the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst. At low POM reaction temperatures (450 °C and
661 550 °C) CO disproportionation reaction occurs producing CO₂ and carbon. On the other
662 hand, the H₂/CO ratio has resulted in all the cases higher than 2. By using steam instead
663 of oxygen no significant carbon deposition has been detected on NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst,
664 but it leads to lower methane conversion and CO yields while it improves the H₂
665 production. By contrast, it has been observed that this change of the composition of the

666 reaction gas mixture is beneficial in the case of the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst. On both nickel
667 aluminate catalysts the main occurrence of water gas shift reaction at low temperature is
668 evident. The combination of POM and SRM gas mixtures seems to increase the
669 CO₂ yield and to decrease CO yields suggesting that there are high combustion activity
670 and low reforming activity.

671 The performance differences, in the three assayed reactions, were related to the Ni
672 particle size which played an important role in the catalytic activity of the two studied
673 catalysts. Furthermore, concerning the behaviour of active metallic Ni species laying on
674 the catalysts, the most important finding reported in this study is the remarkable
675 stability of the reduced NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst, which maintains its small Ni particle size
676 during the reforming reactions. However, the presence of free metallic Ni (with larger
677 size) on the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst, which displayed an increase in its particle size,
678 provokes a decay of its activity and stability.

679

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687

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- Table 1 Characterisation data of the synthesised nickel aluminate catalysts (calcined, reduced and used in POM, SRM and OSRM reactions).
- Table 2 Results from H₂-TPR and XPS studies of the calcined NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP samples.
- Table 3 Values for H₂/CO and CO/CO₂ ratios and coke content in POM, SRM and OSRM reactions over NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts.
- Fig. 1 Mesoporous size distribution for (a) calcined and (b) reduced NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts.
- Fig. 2 XRD patterns of NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts: (a) calcined, (b) reduced, and tested in (c) POM, (d) SRM and (e) OSRM reactions.
- Fig. 3 H₂-TPR profiles of NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts.
- Fig. 4 UV-vis-NIR spectra of NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts.
- Fig. 5 XPS spectra of Ni 2p_{3/2} region (A) and O 1s region (B) of NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts.
- Fig. 6 TEM images and Ni particle size distribution of reduced NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts.
- Fig. 7 NH₃-TPD patterns of (a) calcined and (b) reduced NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts.
- Fig. 8 Methane conversion and H₂, CO and CO₂ yields over reduced NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D catalysts versus reaction temperature in POM, SRM and OSRM reactions. Reactions conditions: 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; W=0.125 g. Gas mixtures: POM: 10%CH₄/5%O₂/N₂, SRM: 10%CH₄/30%H₂O/N₂ and OSRM: 10%CH₄/30%H₂O/5%O₂/N₂. Data corresponding to the commercial 1%Rh/Al₂O₃ catalyst and the thermodynamic equilibrium were also included.
- Fig. 9 Evolution of CH₄ conversion and H₂ and CO yield over the reduced NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts with time on stream in POM reaction at 450, 550 and 650 C. Reactions conditions: 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; W=0.125 g. Gas mixture: 10%CH₄/5%O₂/N₂.
- Fig. 10 TPO-MS analysis over spent NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts after POM reaction.

Samples	Ni ⁽¹⁾ , wt. %	S _{BET} ,	V _p ,	dp, nm	Ni ⁰ size, nm ⁽²⁾	Ni ⁰ size, nm ⁽³⁾	μmol ⁽⁴⁾	μmol ⁽⁴⁾	
		m ² g ⁻¹ 1	cm ³ g ⁻¹ 1				NH ₃ g ⁻¹ 1	NH ₃ m ⁻¹ 2	
Alumina		133	0.55	2.4	-	-	503	3.78	
NiAl ₂ O ₄ -D	Calcined	33	55	0.14	7.5	-	272	4.95	
	Reduced		48	0.12	8.1	23	17.7	274	5.70
	POM		57	0.12	10.7	35	-	-	-
	SRM		47	0.16	11.2	47	-	-	-
	OSRM		37	0.11	9.4	29	-	-	-
NiAl ₂ O ₄ -CP	Calcined	33	76	0.35	15.4	-	291	3.82	
	Reduced		55	0.32	19.2	11	10.6	240	4.38
	POM		64	0.34	18.4	5	-	-	-
	SRM		52	0.33	20.3	11	-	-	-
	OSRM		52	0.32	17.7	7	-	-	-

(1) Determined by WDXRF.

(2) Ni⁰ crystallites size determined by XRD.

(3) Ni⁰ crystallites size determined by TEM.

(4) Total acidity determined by NH₃-TPD.

Catalyst	H ₂ -TPR					XPS				
	Theoretical H ₂ uptake mmol g ⁻¹	Experimental H ₂ uptake mmol g ⁻¹	Relative amount of reducible Ni species, %			Ni/Al	Ni 2p _{3/2}			O 1s
			α^*	β^{**}	γ^{***}		Peak, eV	Ni, % in the sites	Satellite, eV	Peak, eV
NiAl ₂ O ₄ -D	5.7	5.8	33	18	49	1	854.1(1) 856.8(2)	61.7 38.3	861.3	528.5 (a) 531.1 (b) 532.6 (c)
NiAl ₂ O ₄ -CP	5.7	5.6	9	47	44	0.6	855.7 (2)	100	861.8	530.6 (b)

(*) reduction peak of NiO excess

(**) and (***) reduction peaks of Ni²⁺ in nickel aluminate

(1) Ni²⁺ as NiO and (2) Ni²⁺ as NiAl₂O₄.

(a) O²⁻ as NiO, (b) O²⁻ as NiAl₂O₄ and (c) O²⁻ as Al₂O₃

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Table 2

Reaction	Catalyst	H ₂ /CO			CO/CO ₂			Coke, % ⁽¹⁾
		450	550	650	450	550	650	
POM	Equilibrium	21.3	6.0	2.7	0.19	1.06	5.86	-
	NiAl ₂ O ₄ -D	5.5	3.5	2.2	0.24	0.57	3.00	46.5
	NiAl ₂ O ₄ -CP	12.7	4.4	2.5	0.10	0.60	3.00	2.5
	1%Rh/Al ₂ O ₃	2.5	2.8	2.4	0.74	1.29	3.46	2
SRM	Equilibrium	44.9	11.9	6.7	0.10	0.45	1.09	-
	NiAl ₂ O ₄ -D	118.6	19.2	8.5	0.05	0.34	1.03	<1
	NiAl ₂ O ₄ -CP	68.5	13.3	6.9	0.08	0.51	1.42	<1
	1%Rh/Al ₂ O ₃	19.7	12.6	8.2	0.31	0.56	1.06	<1
OSRM	Equilibrium	36.3	12.1	7.3	0.07	0.28	0.56	-
	NiAl ₂ O ₄ -D	43.1	20.1	10.3	0.05	0.16	0.39	<1
	NiAl ₂ O ₄ -CP	55.9	20.1	9.4	0.04	0.18	0.50	<1
	1%Rh/Al ₂ O ₃	8.9	10.8	7.8	0.14	0.31	0.65	<1

787 Reactions conditions: 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; W=0.125 g. Gas mixtures: POM: 10%CH₄/5%O₂/N₂, SRM: 10%CH₄/30%H₂O/N₂ and OSRM: 10%CH₄/30%H₂O/5%O₂/N₂.

788 ⁽¹⁾ Deposited carbon for used catalyst determined by TPO and TG analyses

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Table 3

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Fig. 1

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Fig. 2

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Fig. 3

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Fig. 8

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Fig. 9

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Fig. 10

1 **SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERIZATION AND PERFORMANCE**
2 **EVALUATION OF SPINEL-DERIVED Ni/Al₂O₃ CATALYSTS FOR**
3 **VARIOUS METHANE REFORMING REACTIONS**

4

5

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21 **Abstract**

22 The catalytic performance of bulk nickel aluminate catalysts synthesised by co-
23 precipitation (NiAl₂O₄-CP) and co-dissolution (NiAl₂O₄-D) was examined for various
24 methane reforming reactions, namely partial oxidation, steam reforming and oxidative
25 steam reforming. The calcined and reduced spinels were thoroughly characterised by a
26 wide number of analytical techniques including N₂ physisorption, XRD, UV-visible-
27 NIR DRS, XPS, TEM, H₂-TPR and NH₃-TPD. The characterisation results of the
28 calcined samples at 850 °C showed that nickel aluminate phase was mainly obtained on
29 the NiAl₂O₄-CP near-surface together with a small NiO excess. By contrast, a large
30 amount of NiO phase was formed on NiAl₂O₄-D and deposited on the spinel surface.
31 The reduction at 850 °C of the two samples produced monodispersed Ni particles (10.6
32 nm) in the NiAl₂O₄-CP while larger metallic nickel (17.7 nm) was deposited on the
33 NiAl₂O₄-D. In the three investigated reforming reactions the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst
34 proved to be highly active, stable and resistant toward carbon deposition. Moreover, the
35 performances of the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst appeared to be generally comparable with that
36 of a commercial 1%Rh/Al₂O₃ catalyst. The difference in catalytic behaviour between
37 the two nickel aluminates was related to the Ni dispersion, its particle size and its
38 capacity to minimize the acid character of the alumina by covering a large part of its
39 surface.

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44 *Keywords:* Nickel aluminate, Co-precipitation, Co-dissolution, Ni Crystallite size,
45 Methane reforming

46

47 **1. Introduction**

48 Methane steam reforming (SRM) is the most used technology for producing synthesis
49 gas (CO and H₂) from natural gas [1-5]. Moreover, this technology is a preferable
50 choice for producing clean and larger hydrogen yield. However, because of the high
51 cost of the endothermic character of SRM, the exothermic methane partial oxidation
52 (POM) appears as an alternative as it offers some interesting advantages especially
53 when the posterior use of the syngas stream requires a suitable H₂/CO ratio [6-8].
54 Currently industrial facilities are equipped with systems that offer the possibility of
55 using POM and/or SRM technologies. The combination of the POM and SRM strategies
56 called oxidative steam reforming (OSRM) has the advantage of controlling the process
57 heat and the distribution of the products by adjusting the O/C molar ratio [9-10].

58 Ni-based catalysts are widely used for methane reforming reactions due to their high
59 activity and their competitive costs compared to noble metals [11-13]. Alumina
60 supported Ni systems have particularly received considerable attention because of their
61 practical applications for a variety of reforming reactions [14-18]. Nevertheless, despite
62 exhibiting advantageous catalytic properties, alumina lacks an adequate thermal stability
63 which provokes the sintering of supported metals. Furthermore, the use of alumina as
64 support material has the drawback of rapid deactivation of the catalyst due to carbon
65 deposition on its active acid surface [19-20]. For this reason, the interest of recent
66 investigations has been focused on the preparation of formulations leading to a high
67 dispersion of Ni species which can cover alumina surface, thus minimising the negative
68 effect of its acid character. In this sense, the effect of the addition of some alkali and
69 alkali earth metals, used as chemical promoters, on the activity and stability of
70 Ni/alumina catalysts has been extensively investigated. Typically these additives help to

71 avoid carbon deposition and enhance their stability but at the expense of a reduction of
72 their activity due to the blocking of the more reactive Ni sites [21,22].

73 Within the same objective (the need to improve stability of Ni-based catalysts) nickel
74 aluminate synthesis is one of the routes proposed in the literature for the design of a
75 precursor capable to produce, after its reduction, metallic Ni presenting strong
76 interaction with alumina [14,15,23-25]. For so long, Ross et al. [25] had evidenced the
77 participation of the reduced surface nickel aluminate sites in the steam reforming of
78 methane over Ni/alumina catalysts. Since then, a number of studies dealing with the
79 preparation of nickel aluminate as precursor of active Ni metallic particles for methane
80 reforming reactions are available in the literature. A great majority of these works have
81 been devoted to the investigation of the influence of preparation methods on the
82 stability and the activity of the final formed Ni structures in reforming reactions
83 [14,15,24,26,27]. As stated in various references, it is however complicated to
84 synthesise pure or stoichiometric nickel aluminate by means of conventional methods of
85 synthesis. This is because of the formation of NiO as an excess even when heating at
86 very high temperatures (>1300 °C) [28-30]. Therefore, many works have examined the
87 impact of this particularity on the catalysts performance [15,16,24,27,31].

88 In our previous study, we compared two series of Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts with similar metal
89 content prepared by co-impregnation, using solutions containing a mixture of nickel
90 acetate and aluminium nitrate to obtain a stoichiometric NiAl₂O₄ supported on alumina,
91 and simple impregnation of nickel on alumina [15]. We demonstrated that, in methane
92 steam reforming, the co-impregnated catalyst was more active and we attributed this
93 behaviour to its higher Ni-support interaction. We also noticed that obtaining the active
94 metallic Ni, with small particle size, was controlled by the NiO/NiAl₂O₄ ratio initially
95 present in the calcined samples. Achouri et al. [16] also studied the influence of the

96 preparation method on the catalytic activity in diesel steam reforming of two alumina-
97 supported nickel aluminate catalysts prepared by wet-impregnation and co-precipitation.
98 They concluded that the impregnated catalyst exhibited a higher catalytic performance
99 and stability over time than the co-precipitated counterpart. This different behaviour
100 was explained by the higher carbon deposition tendency shown by the co-precipitated
101 sample.

102 In this paper the influence of the physico-chemical characteristics of two bulk nickel
103 aluminate catalysts, prepared by co-precipitation and co-dissolution methods, on their
104 catalytic behaviour in POM, SRM and OSRM reactions is investigated. To reach this
105 target, an extensive characterisation has been carried out by a wide number of analytical
106 techniques including BET measurements, XRD, XPS, UV-visible-NIR DRS, TEM and
107 H₂-TPR. Likewise, TPD of NH₃, a well-known probe molecule for acid sites, has been
108 used to characterise the surface chemistry of the investigated samples. A special
109 attention has been paid to the determination of the different nickel species formed after
110 high-temperature calcination and subsequent high-temperature reduction. In order to
111 examine and compare their catalytic efficiency the two prepared catalysts were
112 evaluated in partial oxidation, steam reforming and oxidative steam reforming of
113 methane. Interesting conclusions are drawn from the correlation between the
114 distribution of Ni active species of the two catalysts and their performance in these three
115 reforming reactions.

116

117 **2. Experimental**

118 **2.1. Catalysts preparation**

119 Bulk nickel aluminate samples were synthesised by co-precipitation (CP) and co-
120 dissolution (D) methods. The sample named NiAl₂O₄-D was synthesised using two

121 aqueous solutions of $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{-COO})_2\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3\cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Then they were mixed
122 (leading to a mixture with the desired 1:2 Ni/Al molar ratio), and evaporated on a hot
123 plate (150 °C). In the case of $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-CP}$, aqueous ammonia was added to the mixed
124 aqueous solutions to adjust the final suitable pH (=8). For comparative purposes NiO
125 was also prepared by simple calcination in air of $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{-COO})_2\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. All the samples
126 were dried at 110 °C overnight and then calcined at 850 °C in static air for 4 h at a
127 heating rate of 10 °C min^{-1} . Finally, pellets of bulk (nickel aluminate or nickel oxide)
128 samples were prepared by a process of compressing the powders into flakes in a
129 hydraulic press (Specac), crushing and sieving (0.3-0.5 mm).

130

131 **2.2. Catalyst characterisation**

132 The catalysts were characterised by N_2 physisorption at -196 °C, wavelength dispersive
133 X-ray fluorescence (WDXRF), X-ray diffraction (XRD), ultraviolet-visible-near
134 infrared diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy
135 (XPS), temperature programmed reduction with hydrogen ($\text{H}_2\text{-TPR}$) and temperature
136 programmed desorption of NH_3 ($\text{NH}_3\text{-TPD}$). The experimental details of each analytical
137 technique are described elsewhere [14,15]. Additionally, the morphology and particle
138 size distribution of the nickel particles was examined by transmission electron
139 microscopy (TEM). Prior to analysis, the samples were dispersed in absolute ethanol
140 ultrasonically for 30 min, and 10 cm^3 of each sample were then placed on flexible film
141 (Parafilm® M). Glow-discharged carbon-coated copper grids were inverted onto the
142 droplets of each sample. After incubation for 1 min at room temperature, the grids were
143 manually blotted with filter paper air-dried. Digitally recorded 2D images of each
144 solution were taken at room temperature at a nominal magnification of 80000 on a Jeol
145 JEM-1230 transmission electron microscope, with a LaB6 filament as the source of

146 electrons and operated at 100 kV. Digital images were recorded on an Orius SC1000
147 cooled slow-scan CCD camera, 4008×2672 pixels (GATAN), obtaining a final pixel
148 size of 0.85 Å pixel⁻¹. The particle size distribution was obtained from the measurement
149 of at least 300 particles using ImageJ software, and the average diameter was calculated
150 by $d_M = \sum d_i \cdot n_i / \sum n_i$, where n_i is the number of the particles of diameter d_i .

151 On the other hand, the amount of carbonaceous deposits on the used catalyst was
152 determined by dynamic thermogravimetry using a Setaram Setsys Evolution apparatus
153 under atmospheric pressure coupled to a Pfeiffer Prisma mass spectrometer (TPO-MS).
154 The mass loss and the sample temperature were continuously recorded by a
155 computerised data acquisition system. Previously, the samples (20 mg) were dried from
156 room temperature to 150 °C. Then, the temperature was increased from 150 to 850 °C at
157 a constant heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹. The oxidant stream was 5% O₂/He (50 cm³ min⁻¹)
158 flowing downwards onto the cylindrical sample holder.

159

160 **2.3. Catalytic tests**

161 The three methane reforming reactions were studied in a bench-scale fixed-bed reactor
162 operated at atmospheric pressure. The reactor was made of stainless steel with an
163 internal diameter of 9 mm and a height of 305 mm. Prior to the reaction the catalyst
164 (0.125 g) was diluted with inert quartz (0.875 g, 1-1.25 mm). The catalyst bed was
165 maintained in the reactor on a quartz wool plug. The temperature was measured by a
166 thermocouple placed between the particles of the catalyst. Before the reaction the
167 NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts were reduced in situ with a mixture of
168 5% H₂/N₂ at 850 °C for 2 h. Likewise, a 1% Rh/Al₂O₃ (Alfa Aesar, 132 m² g⁻¹)
169 commercial catalyst was reduced at 700 °C and its activity was used for comparative
170 purposes in the three methane reforming reactions.

171 Three different feed gas mixtures balanced with N₂ (38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹) were used
172 in each reforming reaction as follows:

173 i) 10% CH₄ and 5% O₂ in POM reaction.

174 ii) 10% CH₄ and 30% H₂O in SRM reaction.

175 iii) 10% CH₄, 30% H₂O and 5% O₂ in OSRM reaction.

176 The runs were sequentially carried out by increasing and decreasing the reaction
177 temperature (450 °C-550 °C-650 °C-550 °C-450 °C) with an accumulated time online of
178 about 63 h. Catalytic activity, product yields and stability were recorded during 12.5 h
179 at each reaction temperature. Feed and effluent streams were analysed online by a
180 MicroGC (Agilent 3000) equipped with a TCD detector. Two columns, Molecular Sieve
181 5A and Plot U, were used in a series/bypass arrangement for the complete separation of
182 H₂, N₂, O₂, CH₄, CO and CO₂. A cold trap at the outlet of the reactor was used to
183 condense out any water from the product gas stream. On basis of the molar flow at the
184 inlet and outlet of the reactor, conversion and product yields were calculated, according
185 to the following equations:

186
$$X(CH_4), \% = \frac{F(CO_{out}) + F(CO_{2out})}{F(CH_{4in})} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

187
$$Y(H_2) = \frac{F(H_{2out})}{2 \cdot F(CH_{4in})} \quad (2)$$

188
$$Y(CO) = \frac{F(CO_{out})}{F(CH_{4in})} \quad (3)$$

189
$$Y(CO_2) = \frac{F(CO_{2out})}{F(CH_{4in})} \quad (4)$$

190

191

192 **3. Results and discussions**

193 **3.1 Characterisation of the samples**

194 **3.1.1. N₂-physorption (BET measurements)**

195 N₂ adsorption at -196 °C on NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP showed that the isotherms (not
196 shown) were characteristic of mesoporous solids of type IV according to the IUPAC
197 classification. In the case of NiAl₂O₄-D the nitrogen desorption gave rise to a hysteresis
198 loop, H2 type, which was characteristic of disordered porous materials. Table 1 lists the
199 data obtained from the analysis of the textural properties of the calcined and reduced
200 samples. The prepared NiAl₂O₄-CP spinel (76 m² g⁻¹) had a higher surface area than
201 NiAl₂O₄-D (55 m² g⁻¹). This difference probably resulted from the preparation method
202 and the corresponding proportion of NiO formed in each sample. Fig.1 shows the pore
203 sizes distribution for the NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts. The pore size
204 distribution trace for the NiAl₂O₄-D sample exhibited one maximum at 7 nm in the low
205 mesoporous range (<10 nm) whereas the NiAl₂O₄-CP samples exhibited a peak centred
206 at 20 nm. After reduction at high temperature (850 °C) both samples decreased their
207 total surface area (48 m² g⁻¹ for NiAl₂O₄-D and 55 m² g⁻¹ for NiAl₂O₄-CP); however it
208 did not influence considerably their pore size distribution.

209 **3.1.2. X-ray diffraction (XRD)**

210 The general formula of stoichiometric nickel aluminates (spinel structure) is NiAl₂O₄. It
211 crystallizes in the cubic system and belongs to Fd-3m space group [32-36]. Typically,
212 the framework of the “normal” spinel structures consists of an ensemble of tetrahedral
213 and octahedral coordination occupied by bivalent (Ni²⁺) and trivalent (Al³⁺) cations,
214 respectively [32,33]. However, this distribution can change when the Ni²⁺ partially
215 adopts the octahedral site while the tetrahedral site hosts the Al³⁺ together with Ni²⁺

ions. This structural flexibility generates a family of compounds of inverse spinel structure described as $\text{Ni}_{1-x}\text{Al}_x[\text{Ni}_x\text{Al}_{2-x}]\text{O}_4$ ($0 < x < 1$) [32-36].

The NiAl_2O_4 -D and NiAl_2O_4 -CP samples were characterized by means of X-ray powder diffraction in order to investigate their structural properties. Fig. 2 compares the diffractograms of the catalysts before and after reduction at 850 °C. The patterns of the calcined NiAl_2O_4 -D and NiAl_2O_4 -CP revealed the formation of the spinel structure (JCPDS 78-1601). Furthermore, in the case of NiAl_2O_4 -D catalyst additional peaks associated with NiO structure, at 43.5° and 63.1°, were observed whereas the diffractogram of NiAl_2O_4 -CP showed no lines of NiO. A more careful analysis of the pattern of NiAl_2O_4 -D evidenced that the intensity ratio of the peaks corresponding to (220) and (440) reticular planes differed from that of NiAl_2O_4 -CP. This difference could be explained by the cation distribution in the octahedral and tetrahedral sites affecting the inversion degree of the spinel structure. The diffraction lines associated with the (220) plane are related to the tetrahedrally-coordinated cations while the diffraction signals belonging to the (440) plane are attributed to both tetrahedrally and octahedrally-coordinated cations [34-36]. From our experimental data $I(220)/I(440)$ ratios were estimated. For the NiAl_2O_4 -CP catalyst this ratio was 0.22, whereas it increased up to 0.33 for the NiAl_2O_4 -D. The increase in $I(220)/I(440)$ ratio was also observed by Wang et al. [35] in XRD patterns of various inverse spinel structures. This feature was assigned to the increasing occupancy of the heavier cations on the tetrahedral sites. We might accordingly conclude that on the NiAl_2O_4 -D catalyst nickel was preferentially hosted in tetrahedral sites of the inverse spinel whereas nickel tended to occupy the octahedral coordination in the case of NiAl_2O_4 -CP sample prepared by co-precipitation.

240 Fig. 2 also includes the X-ray diffraction patterns of the bulk nickel aluminates reduced
241 at 850 °C. A comparison of the patterns before and after reduction confirmed that the
242 transformation of Ni²⁺ ions of the spinel framework into metallic Ni (JCPDS 89-7128)
243 was complete. Likewise, the formation of alumina structure (JCPDS 79-1558) instead of
244 the characteristic peaks attributed to spinel structure was noted. However, in the case of
245 the NiAl₂O₄-D sample, diffraction peaks with a low intensity attributed to NiO were
246 also observed. This could be reasonably explained by the surface room temperature
247 passivation of the catalyst [31]. Table 1 reports the metallic Ni crystallite size,
248 calculated by Scherrer equation, by using Ni (200) (2θ = 51.6°) diffraction line
249 broadening. The average size of Ni particles was found to be around 11 nm on the
250 reduced NiAl₂O₄-CP while larger particles with an average size of about 23 nm were
251 detected for the reduced NiAl₂O₄-D.

252 In sum, the obtained XRD results indicated that the preparation method of nickel
253 aluminate had an important effect on the excess of NiO and the Ni²⁺ ions distribution,
254 between tetrahedral and octahedral sites in the spinel structure. Moreover, the reduction
255 of the NiAl₂O₄-CP sample prepared by co-precipitation method produced smaller Ni
256 particles in comparison with the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst.

257 **3.1.3. Temperature programmed reduction (H₂-TPR)**

258 The TPR experiments were performed in order to determine the different Ni reducible
259 species present in the two prepared spinel catalysts (Fig. 3). It was observed that the
260 shape of the TPR traces depended on the preparation method. The thermogram of the
261 NiAl₂O₄-D sample displayed a typical reduction spectrum of a mixture of two Ni
262 species consisting of free NiO (α-peak at 400 °C) and nickel aluminates structures (β-
263 peak at 600 °C and γ-peak at 800 °C) [14-15]. In the case of NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst it was
264 noted that the characteristic reduction peak attributed to bulk NiO (at 400 °C) was

265 absent. The observed three H₂ uptakes in the profile of the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst were
266 located at 520, 750 and 825 °C. The peak at 520 °C was attributed to the highly
267 dispersed NiO. Generally, the NiO reduction peak shifts towards high temperatures, as
268 in the case of NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst, when the NiO particles strongly interact with the
269 support [31]. Above 600 °C, the high-temperature reduction peaks at 750 and 825 °C
270 were due to the reduction of Ni²⁺ ions incorporated in the nickel aluminate structure.
271 The relative abundance of the NiO species in the NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP samples
272 was estimated to be 33% and 9%, respectively (Table 2). Note that the XRD pattern of
273 the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst showed that no peaks due to NiO were observed probably
274 because of its low amount and/or its high dispersion.

275 Though it was reported that free NiO present on the spinel reduces at low temperature
276 and favours the reduction of nickel located in the spinel [24], to our knowledge, the real
277 origin of the splitting of the nickel aluminates peak reduction has never been discussed.
278 As deduced from our XRD study, on the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst, nickel mainly has a
279 tetrahedral coordination whereas it was mainly octahedrally coordinated in the case of
280 NiAl₂O₄-CP. We believe that the two observed reduction peaks and their position could
281 be related to the different Ni²⁺ coordination in the spinel framework. Furthermore, since
282 the contribution of the β-peak in the total Ni species present in the spinel structure of
283 NiAl₂O₄-D was lower (27%) than that of NiAl₂O₄-CP (51%), it could be concluded that
284 Ni²⁺ ions occupying octahedral sites were more prone to be reduced than the tetrahedral
285 ones.

286 **3.1.4. UV–visible–NIR diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS)**

287 The coordination and the oxidation state of nickel species on the NiAl₂O₄-D and
288 NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts were studied by means of diffuse reflectance spectroscopy. Fig. 4
289 showed the UV-visible-NIR spectra of the two prepared samples and the spectrum of

290 pure NiO presented as reference. The shape of NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D spectra
291 resulted almost identical. All the spectra displayed a strong absorption in the UV
292 domain. The maxima centred at 220-345 nm were ascribed to O²⁻ → Ni²⁺ metal to
293 ligand charge transfers [14, 15, 37]. In the visible range, the bands located at 380 nm
294 and 720 nm were associated with ν_3 (³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (P)) and ν_2 (³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}) absorptions
295 that resulted from d-d transitions of Ni²⁺ ions hosted by octahedral sites [14,15,37,38].
296 The spectra were also characterised by the presence of an additional intense band in the
297 range of 600–645 nm and shoulders at 550 nm and 760 nm, assigned to the
298 (³T₁(F) → ³T_{1g} (P)) ligand transitions, thereby evidencing the presence of the
299 tetrahedrally coordinated Ni²⁺ ions.

300 In the NIR a broad resolved band located around 1130 nm was observed which was
301 ascribed to the ν_1 (³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}) transition of Ni²⁺ in octahedral symmetry [14,15,37,38].
302 Comparing the intensity of this absorption band it was clear that the relative abundance
303 of octahedral Ni²⁺ ions in NiAl₂O₄-CP was superior to that of NiAl₂O₄-D. This was in
304 accordance with the results obtained by XRD. However, the quantification of tetrahedral
305 Ni²⁺ ions on the spectra was difficult because of the overlapping of the absorption
306 domains of Ni²⁺ ions in tetrahedral and octahedral symmetries.

307 On the other hand, it should be pointed out that the spectrum of NiAl₂O₄-D exhibited
308 two additional shoulders: (i) the first one was located around 420 nm, (ii) the second
309 one at a wavelength of 450 nm. Since the presence of these bands was also detected in
310 the spectrum of NiO, they could be assigned to d–d transitions caused by the ligand
311 field of unsupported NiO. These bands were expectedly absent from the spectrum of
312 NiAl₂O₄-CP, thus confirming that NiO was exclusively formed on the calcined
313 NiAl₂O₄-D. These results suggested, in line with XRD characterisation, that in contrast
314 to NiAl₂O₄-CP, the preparation of NiAl₂O₄-D led to the formation of nickel aluminate

315 together with NiO structure. Furthermore, these evidences could reasonably explain the
316 greenish-blue colour of the NiAl₂O₄-D sample and the dark blue colour of NiAl₂O₄-CP.

317 **3.1.5. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)**

318 The chemical composition and the distribution of nickel species laying on the surface of
319 the calcined NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D catalysts were investigated by means of XPS
320 measurements. The Ni 2p_{3/2} and O 1s photoemission peaks for the two analysed samples
321 were shown in Fig. 5. The different broadness and the symmetry of the Ni 2p_{3/2} and O 1s
322 main peaks for NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D oxides were evident. As revealed by the
323 analysis of the spectra included in Fig. 5 the NiAl₂O₄-D sample showed much broader
324 and less symmetric peaks, thus suggesting a larger heterogeneity in its nickel
325 environments. On the basis of these observations the Ni 2p_{3/2} and O 1s spectra of
326 NiAl₂O₄-D were deconvoluted. As a result, the main Ni 2p_{3/2} XPS peak displayed two
327 bands. The first one located at 854.1 eV was associated with NiO exhibiting weak
328 interaction NiO-NiAl₂O₄ [15]. The second one, centred at 856.8 eV, was related to
329 Ni²⁺ ions in the network of nickel aluminates [15]. On the other hand, the O 1s signal of
330 the NiAl₂O₄-D XPS spectrum could be decomposed into three components: the first one
331 at 528.5 eV assigned to O²⁻ in NiO, the second situated at 531.1 eV due to
332 NiAl₂O₄ phase and the third one located at high binding energies 532.6 eV characteristic
333 of pure Al₂O₃ [15]. By contrast, because of their apparent symmetry the O 1s and
334 Ni 2p_{3/2} signals of NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst suggested the presence of a unique phase. The
335 comparison of the positions of the O 1s (530.6 eV) and Ni 2p_{3/2} (855.7 eV) peaks with
336 the attributions mentioned above revealed that the NiAl₂O₄-CP near-surface was mainly
337 composed of nickel aluminate structure. Note that despite of the fact that the occurrence
338 of the small fraction of NiO phase was detected for this sample by H₂-TPR, its XPS
339 spectra did not reveal the presence of this species. This might be explained by the strong

340 interaction of the highly dispersed NiO with NiAl₂O₄ phase that was reflected by the
341 shifting of its XPS peak towards higher binding energy.

342 The difference in Ni/Al atomic ratio determined by XPS between NiAl₂O₄-CP and
343 NiAl₂O₄-D also supported our conclusion about the structural composition of near-
344 surface. According to Table 2, the Ni/Al atomic ratio of NiAl₂O₄-CP (0.6) was smaller
345 than that determined for NiAl₂O₄-D (1), suggesting that the surface of the co-
346 precipitated sample was comparatively deficient in nickel. Thus, in view of the
347 stoichiometry of the pure spinel (Ni/Al=0.5), it could be concluded that nickel
348 aluminate phase was mainly obtained on the NiAl₂O₄-CP near-surface together with a
349 small NiO excess. A larger amount of NiO phase was however formed on NiAl₂O₄-D.

350 **3.1.6. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)**

351 NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D samples, reduced at 850 °C, were investigated by
352 transmission electron microscopy as well. Fig. 6(a) and 6(b) show the TEM
353 micrographs and size distribution diagrams (obtained from the measurement of about
354 300 particles). The micrographs of both samples showed no significant differences in
355 morphology. In both cases spherical particles of nickel were observed. Nevertheless, it
356 was visualised that nickel was homogeneously dispersed in NiAl₂O₄-CP while it was
357 much more heterogeneous on the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst. The particle size distribution in
358 the co-precipitated sample presented a unimodal shape with an average size of 10.6 nm
359 (dispersion of 9.5%). By contrast a broad distribution ranging from 10 to 50 nm was
360 obtained for the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst with a corresponding average size of 17.7 nm
361 (dispersion of 4%). By correlating the Ni particle size distributions with the results of
362 H₂-TPR, XRD, XPS and UV-Visible-NIR DRS it could be reasonably assumed that the
363 smaller mono-dispersed particles present on the NiAl₂O₄-CP corresponded to particles
364 resulted from the reduction of nickel aluminate phase whereas the range of larger

365 particles deposited on the NiAl₂O₄-D was originated by the reduction of the free NiO.
366 As stated previously, the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst contained two Ni species as a mixture of
367 free NiO and nickel aluminate phase while NiAl₂O₄-CP was composed mainly by nickel
368 aluminate together with a relatively small fraction of highly dispersed NiO (as proved
369 by H₂-TPR). Furthermore, we thought that the difference between NiAl₂O₄-D and
370 NiAl₂O₄-CP probably resulted from the textural properties of each catalyst as well. The
371 NiAl₂O₄-D average pore size was smaller (7.5 nm) compared to its Ni particles average
372 size, suggesting that nickel was mainly deposited on the external surface. However, the
373 NiAl₂O₄-CP average pore size was around 15 nm and this might limit the growth of the
374 Ni crystallites during the reduction.

375 **3.1.7. Temperature programmed desorption of NH₃ (NH₃-TPD)**

376 The surface acidity of the two catalysts was characterised by means of temperature
377 programmed desorption using ammonia as probe molecule (Fig. 7). The deconvolution
378 of the NH₃-TPD thermograms exhibited two bands corresponding to two types of acid
379 sites. The first one consisted of a peak located at low temperatures (<220 °C)
380 accompanied by a second much more intense feature at relatively high temperatures
381 (250-370 °C), the latter being probably due to a fraction of strong acid sites present at
382 the surface of the catalysts. The obtained quantitative results were summarised in Table
383 1. It was found that the surface density of NH₃ desorbed from the calcined NiAl₂O₄-CP,
384 3.82 μmol NH₃ m⁻², was smaller than that determined for the calcined NiAl₂O₄-D,
385 4.95 μmol NH₃ m⁻². The difference could be related to the structural composition of
386 each catalyst. As demonstrated by XPS analysis the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst contained
387 alumina phase in its near-surface which could improve its surface acid properties. It
388 should be pointed out that the H₂ reduction at 850 °C of the two catalysts appeared to
389 increase both the amount and the thermal stability of the adsorbed NH₃ by shifting the

390 desorption peaks towards higher temperatures. The acid surface density for reduced
391 $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-CP}$ was estimated to reach $4.38 \mu\text{mol NH}_3 \text{ m}^{-2}$ in comparison with
392 $5.7 \mu\text{mol NH}_3 \text{ m}^{-2}$ for $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-D}$ (Table 1). These results might be related to the
393 formation of alumina instead of nickel aluminate structure in the two reduced samples,
394 as proved by XRD analysis. In addition, the presence of homogeneous and highly
395 dispersed nickel in the reduced $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-CP}$ catalyst, as confirmed by TEM analysis,
396 could explain the occurrence of a small fraction of surface acid sites in comparison with
397 $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-D}$. By contrast, the low Ni dispersion (4%) on the latter led to a large
398 uncovered acid support surface.

399

400 **3.2. Catalytic activity**

401 **3.2.1 Partial oxidation of methane (POM)**

402 The POM reaction was carried out on the activated (calcination followed by reduction)
403 $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-CP}$, $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-D}$ and 1%Rh/ Al_2O_3 (used as reference) catalysts, at 450, 550 and
404 650 °C, by sequentially increasing the reaction temperature with 100 °C intervals. The
405 inverse sequence was conducted by decreasing the reaction temperature (from 650 to
406 550 and 450 °C) in order to probe the stability of the catalysts. Fig. 8 show the obtained
407 results in terms of CH_4 conversion and H_2 , CO and CO_2 yields. The corresponding
408 equilibrium data are included as well (calculated via the HSC Chemistry software
409 package by the GIBBS program using the so-called Gibbs Energy Minimization
410 Method). The reported data evidenced that the $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-CP}$ catalyst was typically more
411 active than the $\text{NiAl}_2\text{O}_4\text{-D}$. Furthermore, over the co-precipitated sample methane
412 conversion as well as H_2 , CO and CO_2 yields were fairly stable during 12.5 h on stream.
413 At 450 °C the conversion on this sample was around 25% and it increased to reach
414 about 36% at 550 °C and 58% at 650 °C. Likewise, the increase in the reaction

415 temperature promoted the H₂ yield, which attained 0.56. Carbon monoxide production
416 also increased up to 0.44 at 650 °C. It is noteworthy that at 650 °C both conversion and
417 yields achieved with NiAl₂O₄-CP were close to the values obtained with the commercial
418 1%Rh/Al₂O₃ catalyst. As the performance of the noble metal-based catalyst is
419 considered as reference in the POM reaction [39-42], these catalytic features evidenced
420 the potential of NiAl₂O₄-CP as a promising alternative catalyst. By contrast, the activity
421 appeared to decrease with time on stream in the case of NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst. As shown
422 in Fig. 9, methane conversion at 450 °C gradually decreased from 29% at the beginning
423 of the reaction to 25% after 12.5 h on stream. Likewise, H₂, CO and CO₂ yields were
424 not stable with time on line. Indeed, a slight increase in activity followed by a stable
425 plateau was observed when the reaction temperature decreased suggesting that an
426 activation of the catalyst occurred with time-on-stream (Fig. 9).

427 Table 3 lists the H₂/CO and CO/CO₂ ratios calculated for each reaction temperature on
428 the tested catalysts. Note that, on the two tested nickel catalysts, the CO/CO₂ ratio
429 seemed to increase with reaction temperature. For instance, at 450 °C the CO/CO₂ ratio
430 on the NiAl₂O₄-CP was around 0.1 and it increased to reach about 3 at 650 °C. At low
431 CO/CO₂ values (corresponding to relatively low temperatures) CO disproportionation
432 reaction may occur producing CO₂ and carbon. On the other hand, the H₂/CO ratio was
433 in all the cases higher than 2 (ranging between 2.2 and 2.5). It is widely accepted that
434 the encapsulation of the metal particles by deposited carbon does not occur if H₂/CO or
435 H₂O/hydrocarbon ratios are sufficiently high [43]. Accordingly, our results showed, by
436 comparing the NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D catalysts, that the catalyst with the highest
437 H₂/CO ratio (NiAl₂O₄-CP) did not suffer apparent deactivation.

438 Thermogravimetric (not shown) and TPO-MS analyses (Fig. 10) performed in order to
439 determine the amount of carbon accumulated on the used catalysts in POM resulted in

440 deposited carbon masses of 2.4 wt.% on NiAl₂O₄-CP (close to 2 wt% observed for the
441 commercial rhodium catalyst) and 46.5 wt.% on NiAl₂O₄-D (Table 3). Both TPO traces
442 consisted of a CO₂ production major peak at approximately 670 °C (Fig. 10). Thus, the
443 same type of carbonaceous species was present on the two catalysts. It could be
444 concluded, therefore, that the deactivation of NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst might mainly occur as
445 a result of the substantial formation of coke. This was in agreement with XRD analysis
446 of the spent catalysts which confirmed the formation of carbon (graphite) on the two
447 catalysts. Specially, it was observed that the principal peak (26.4°) was much more
448 intense in the NiAl₂O₄-D diffractogram than that of NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst (Fig. 2). On
449 the other hand, the Ni (200) (2θ = 51.6°) diffraction line broadening was used to
450 estimate, by Scherrer equation, the evolution of metallic Ni crystallite size after catalytic
451 test (Table 1). It was found that the growth of Ni⁰ crystallites during POM reaction on
452 NiAl₂O₄-D for extended periods of time was significant (size estimated to be around
453 23 nm in the reduced sample while it was around 35 nm after catalytic test). In
454 agreement with a previous study which reported that, in the methane reforming
455 reactions, the larger Ni crystallites on the Ni catalyst favoured the formation of graphitic
456 carbon [44], we could conclude that the same phenomenon occurred in the case of our
457 NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst. As stated previously, the reduction of the Ni species deposited on
458 this sample produced large metallic Ni which was less resistant to sintering and coke
459 formation.

460 The XRD diffractograms of the spent nickel aluminate catalysts also evidenced the
461 presence of NiO phase (Fig. 2). The NiO characteristic peaks were much more intense
462 on the NiAl₂O₄-CP diffractogram suggesting that the oxidation of Ni species during the
463 POM reaction was influenced by their interaction with the support. Accordingly, it
464 seemed that the oxidation of the smaller Ni particles, during POM reaction, might be

465 easier. Indeed, our H₂-TPR and TEM studies indicated that more than two distinct
466 metallic nickel populations were present on NiAl₂O₄-D in contrast with the NiAl₂O₄-CP
467 catalyst with a narrower and more homogeneous size distribution (size = 10.6 nm). In
468 their study on the mechanism for POM reaction, Jin et al. [45] claimed that during the
469 CH₄/O₂ reaction over Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts, Ni⁰ was first oxidised to NiO, and the latter
470 was reduced again by CH₄ during the transient process. Since the reduction of NiO by
471 CH₄ is endothermic and as the last step of our catalytic experiments occurred at 450 °C
472 (relatively low temperature) the presence of the characteristic peaks of NiO in our XRD
473 diffractograms of the used samples could be justified.

474 On the other hand, as described in previous works the carbon deposition may deactivate
475 the catalyst either by covering of the active sites and/or by pore blocking [43-46]. In our
476 case, it was found that, after catalytic tests, the pore size distribution of NiAl₂O₄-D
477 catalyst shifted towards higher values (8.1 nm to 10.7 nm) suggesting the blocking of
478 the pores with small sizes by carbon deposition (Table 1). In addition, it should be noted
479 that carbon deposition on the NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D catalysts appeared to
480 significantly increase the surface area (Table 1). Thus, on NiAl₂O₄-D the specific
481 surface area increased from 48 to 57 m² g⁻¹ whereas over NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst it
482 increased from 55 to 64 m² g⁻¹, suggesting that this might be due to the similar porous
483 nature of the carbon deposited on the two catalysts [46].

484 On the other hand, the chemical properties of their near surface could have an effect on
485 the catalytic activity and stability of NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts. Generally,
486 acidity is considered to induce a negative impact on methane reforming behaviour by
487 catalysing the coke formation [43]. In agreement with our NH₃-TPD studies, the surface
488 of NiAl₂O₄-D bears more acid sites than that of NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst. This difference in

489 the acid character could explain the markedly larger formation of coke on the surface of
490 the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst in comparison with NiAl₂O₄-CP.

491 In addition, the inversion degree of the formed spinel was another factor to take into
492 consideration in order to explain the different performances of NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-
493 CP in POM reaction. In their study on the methane dry reforming reaction over nickel
494 aluminate catalysts Kathiraser et al. [26] concluded that the inverse NiAl₂O₄ spinel
495 structure positively affected the catalytic activity compared to the normal spinel. Our
496 characterization results showed that NiAl₂O₄-CP tended to be in the inverse
497 coordination while the NiAl₂O₄-D was close to the normal spinel phase. The observed
498 divergence between NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP might influence the catalytic
499 behaviour of these catalysts as well.

500 **3.2.2. Steam reforming of methane (SRM)**

501 Fig. 8 show CH₄ conversion and H₂, CO and CO₂ yields in the SRM reaction for the
502 examined reduced catalysts as function of temperature. In all cases methane conversion
503 as well as H₂, CO and CO₂ yields were stable with time on stream. Moreover, the
504 NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D catalysts were markedly more active than
505 1%Rh/Al₂O₃ (80% and 53% vs. 46% at 650 °C, respectively). The comparison of the
506 performance of the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst in POM and SRM reactions showed that
507 replacing oxygen with steam resulted in poorer methane conversion and CO yield while
508 it improved the H₂ production. By contrast, when compared to its performance in POM
509 reaction, an increase in activity as well as CO and H₂ yields were observed over
510 NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst in SRM reaction, especially at 550 °C and 650 °C. Furthermore,
511 among the three catalysts the best methane conversion and the largest H₂, CO and CO₂
512 yields were achieved with NiAl₂O₄-CP at the three reaction temperatures. Thus, at
513 450 °C the NiAl₂O₄-D and 1%Rh/Al₂O₃ catalysts exhibited a poor performance as their

514 activity did not exceed 10% (the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst gave a conversion of 21% at this
515 temperature). It should be noted that the CO production, at 450 °C, was very low or
516 negligible over the three tested catalysts. However, considerable yields of CO₂ (0.18
517 over NiAl₂O₄-CP and 0.07 over NiAl₂O₄-D) and H₂ (0.5 over NiAl₂O₄-CP and 0.22
518 over NiAl₂O₄-D) were obtained suggesting the main occurrence of water gas shift
519 reaction. On the effect of the SRM reaction temperature on the catalytic performance of
520 the Ni catalysts, we noted that higher temperatures improved conversion which rapidly
521 increased to reach about 80% and 53% over NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D respectively
522 (at 650 °C). Likewise, irrespective of the used catalyst both H₂ and CO yields increased
523 as the SRM reaction temperature increased. This trend was more pronounced on the
524 NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst which led to CO (0.47 at 650 °C) and H₂ (1.6 at 650 °C) yields and
525 a H₂/CO ratio close to the thermodynamic equilibrium.

526 On the other hand, as expected, the activity of the three catalysts was not accompanied
527 by the carbon deposition (Table 3) which might be explained by adding water to the
528 feed with a high H₂O/CH₄ ratio (around 3). The observed H₂/CO ratio was in all the
529 cases higher than 6. As no significant carbon deposition was detected (Table 3), one
530 could conclude that this was the reason for the stability of the NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-
531 CP tested catalysts. Note that, for both NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts, no
532 significant loss of their surface area was observed. XRD patterns of the NiAl₂O₄-D and
533 NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts recorded after the tests did not show any noticeable difference
534 when compared with that of the freshly reduced samples suggesting that they did not
535 undergo any noticeable alteration of their crystalline structures during the reaction
536 (Fig. 2). However, an appreciable increase of Ni particle size was noticed in the case of
537 NiAl₂O₄-D. Since this did not affect its catalytic stability the Ni particles growth was
538 supposed to rapidly occur at the start of the reaction. This behaviour could be related

539 with the nature of the Ni species deposited and their interactions with the carrier. Our
540 characterisation results showed that the difference between the two NiAl₂O₄-CP and
541 NiAl₂O₄-D catalysts was related to the fact that the reduction of the Ni species produced
542 monodispersed fixed nickel on the first one whereas it produced larger particles of free
543 nickel on the second one. On the effect of this distribution we could conclude, then, that
544 the growth of Ni particles in SRM reaction, observed exclusively on NiAl₂O₄-D
545 catalyst, concerned only the free deposited metallic Ni.

546 **3.2.3. Oxidative steam reforming of methane (OSRM)**

547 Finally the catalytic performance in OSRM reaction was also studied and the results are
548 collected in Fig. 8. At the three investigated reaction temperatures the best methane
549 conversion and the largest H₂ and CO yields, over the Ni catalysts, were achieved with
550 the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst. Moreover, compared to its behaviour in POM reaction, a
551 significant improvement of the catalytic activity could be noted; especially at 450 °C
552 and 550 °C reaction temperatures where it was even more active than the 1%Rh/Al₂O₃
553 catalyst. By contrast, the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst clearly gave the lowest methane
554 conversion. Furthermore, the BET surface area of this sample decreased from 48 to
555 37 m² g⁻¹ after reaction. Nevertheless, the water addition to the feed significantly
556 improved the catalytic stability of NiAl₂O₄-D with respect to the POM reaction. Indeed,
557 the literature reported that the excess of water or oxygen to the feed cleans the metallic
558 surface and improve the stability of the catalyst [47]. Accordingly, our estimation of
559 deposited coke, by thermogravimetric and TPO-MS analysis, was less than 1%wt. on
560 both NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts. On the other hand, the combination of POM
561 and SRM gas mixtures seemed to increase the CO₂ yield, which attained 0.41 on the
562 NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst at 650 °C. Moreover, CO/CO₂ ratio did not exceed 0.5, which
563 could be explained by a high combustion activity and a low reforming activity [10].

564 Fig. 2 also shows the XRD patterns of the NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts used in
565 OSRM reaction. The absence of 26.4° diffraction peak indicated that, on both catalysts,
566 no graphite carbon deposition occurred during the tests. By contrast, changes in the Ni
567 crystallite size were noted. For the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst the Ni particle size increased
568 from 22 up to 29 nm, whereas for the NiAl₂O₄-CP it decreased from 11 to 7 nm
569 (Table 1). Similar changes were observed on the XRD patterns of the latter in POM
570 reaction suggesting that a re-distribution of Ni active phases might have occurred which
571 favoured its activity and stability. However, on the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst this re-
572 distribution (increased Ni particle size) provoked the decay of its activity. The XRD
573 diffractograms of the used NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts in OSRM reaction also
574 showed the presence of intense diffraction peaks attributed to the NiO phase (Fig. 2). A
575 similar behaviour was reported by Yoshida et al. [10] in their study of OSR reaction
576 over Ni/ α -Al₂O₃ and they explained it by the oxidation of the Ni species in the presence
577 of gas-phase oxygen. The formation of these Ni oxidised species could explain the high
578 activity of our Ni catalysts for methane combustion.

579 **4. Conclusions**

580 The behaviour of two bulk nickel aluminate (NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D) has been
581 investigated in the partial oxidation, steam reforming and oxidative steam reforming of
582 methane. These catalysts have been prepared by co-precipitation and co-dissolution
583 methods, respectively, and characterised by N₂ physisorption, XRD, UV-visible-NIR
584 DRS, XPS, TEM, H₂-TPR and NH₃-TPD.

585 XRD, H₂-TPR, UV-visible spectroscopy and XPS analyses show that the two catalysts,
586 calcined at 850 °C, contain nickel aluminate as a major phase together with NiO which
587 was considered as an excess. Moreover, it has been proved that on the NiAl₂O₄-D
588 catalyst nickel is preferentially hosted in tetrahedral sites of the inverse spinel whereas it

589 tends to occupy the octahedral coordination in the case of NiAl₂O₄-CP sample. As
590 showed by H₂-TPR, the interaction of the resulted NiO excess with the nickel aluminate
591 seems to depend on the preparation method. Indeed, the reduction of this NiO excess on
592 the NiAl₂O₄-D occurs at lower temperatures compared to the NiAl₂O₄-CP suggesting
593 that on the latter NiO has a strong interaction with nickel aluminate. TEM results
594 indicate that on the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst the reduction of the Ni species at 850 °C
595 produces homogeneous and monodispersed fixed nickel whereas heterogeneous and
596 larger metallic free nickel is detected on the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst. In addition, this
597 distribution has a marked effect on the chemical properties of the reduced catalysts
598 since the surface of reduced NiAl₂O₄-D contains more acid sites than that of reduced
599 NiAl₂O₄-CP.

600 A clearly different behaviour in the reforming of methane has been observed over the
601 NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D catalysts with same Ni composition but prepared by two
602 different methods. The results show that the reforming efficiency is highly dependent on
603 the type of interaction of the Ni active phase with the carrier. In the three tested
604 reforming reactions the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst, prepared by co-precipitation method, has
605 proved to be highly active and stable. However, as a result of the carbon deposition
606 found in POM reaction, methane conversion, H₂, CO and CO₂ yields are not stable with
607 time over the NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst. At low POM reaction temperatures (450 °C and
608 550 °C) CO disproportionation reaction occurs producing CO₂ and carbon. On the other
609 hand, the H₂/CO ratio has resulted in all the cases higher than 2. By using steam instead
610 of oxygen no significant carbon deposition has been detected on NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst,
611 but it leads to lower methane conversion and CO yields while it improves the H₂
612 production. By contrast, it has been observed that this change of the composition of the
613 reaction gas mixture is beneficial in the case of the NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst. On both nickel

614 aluminate catalysts the main occurrence of water gas shift reaction at low temperature is
615 evident. The combination of POM and SRM gas mixtures seems to increase the
616 CO₂ yield and to decrease CO yields suggesting that there are high combustion activity
617 and low reforming activity.

618 Concerning the behaviour of active metallic Ni species laying on the catalysts, the most
619 important finding reported in this study is the remarkable stability of the reduced
620 NiAl₂O₄-CP catalyst, which maintains its Ni particle size during the reforming
621 reactions. However, the presence of free metallic Ni (with larger size) on the NiAl₂O₄-D
622 catalyst, which displayed an increase in its particle size, provokes a decay of its activity
623 and stability.

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772

- Table 1 Characterisation data of the synthesised nickel aluminate catalysts (calcined, reduced and used in POM, SRM and OSRM reactions).
- Table 2 Results from H₂-TPR and XPS studies of the calcined NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP samples.
- Table 3 Values for H₂/CO and CO/CO₂ ratios and coke content in POM, SRM and OSRM reactions over NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts.
- Fig. 1 Mesoporous size distribution for (a) calcined and (b) reduced NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts.
- Fig. 2 XRD patterns of NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts: (a) calcined, (b) reduced, and tested in (c) POM, (d) SRM and (e) OSRM reactions.
- Fig. 3 H₂-TPR profiles of NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts.
- Fig. 4 UV-vis-NIR spectra of NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts.
- Fig. 5 XPS spectra of Ni 2p_{3/2} region (A) and O 1s region (B) of NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts.
- Fig. 6 TEM images and Ni particle size distribution of reduced NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts.
- Fig. 7 NH₃-TPD patterns of (a) calcined and (b) reduced NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts.
- Fig. 8 Methane conversion and H₂, CO and CO₂ yields over reduced NiAl₂O₄-CP and NiAl₂O₄-D catalysts versus reaction temperature in POM, SRM and OSRM reactions. Reactions conditions: 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; W=0.125 g. Gas mixtures: POM: 10%CH₄/5%O₂/N₂, SRM: 10%CH₄/30%H₂O/N₂ and OSRM: 10%CH₄/30%H₂O/5%O₂/N₂. Data corresponding to the commercial 1%Rh/Al₂O₃ catalyst and the thermodynamic equilibrium were also included.
- Fig. 9 Evolution of CH₄ conversion and H₂ and CO yield over the reduced NiAl₂O₄-D catalyst with time on stream in POM reaction at 450, 550 and 650 C. Reactions conditions: 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; W=0.125 g. Gas mixture: 10%CH₄/5%O₂/N₂.
- Fig. 10 TPO-MS analysis over spent NiAl₂O₄-D and NiAl₂O₄-CP catalysts after POM reaction.

Samples	Ni ⁽¹⁾ , wt. %	S _{BET} , m ² g ⁻¹	V _p , cm ³ g ⁻¹	dp, nm	Ni ⁰ size, nm ⁽²⁾	Ni ⁰ size, nm ⁽³⁾	μmol ⁽⁴⁾ NH ₃ g ⁻¹	μmol ⁽⁴⁾ NH ₃ m ⁻²	
Alumina		133	0.55	2.4	-	-	503	3.78	
NiAl ₂ O ₄ -D	Calcined	33	55	0.14	7.5	-	272	4.95	
	Reduced		48	0.12	8.1	23	17.7	274	5.70
	POM		57	0.12	10.7	35	-	-	-
	SRM		47	0.16	11.2	47	-	-	-
	OSRM		37	0.11	9.4	29	-	-	-
NiAl ₂ O ₄ -CP	Calcined	33	76	0.35	15.4	-	291	3.82	
	Reduced		55	0.32	19.2	11	10.6	240	4.38
	POM		64	0.34	18.4	5	-	-	-
	SRM		52	0.33	20.3	11	-	-	-
	OSRM		52	0.32	17.7	7	-	-	-

(1) Determined by WDXRF.

(2) Ni⁰ crystallites size determined by XRD.

(3) Ni⁰ crystallites size determined by TEM.

(4) Total acidity determined by NH₃-TPD.

Catalyst	H ₂ -TPR			XPS				
	Relative amount of reducible Ni species, %			Ni/Al	Ni 2p _{3/2}			O 1s
	α^*	β^{**}	γ^{***}		Peak, eV	Ni, % in the sites	Satellite, eV	Peak, eV
NiAl ₂ O ₄ -D	33	18	49	1	854.1(1) 856.8(2)	61.7 38.3	861.3	528.5 (a) 531.1 (b) 532.6 (c)
NiAl ₂ O ₄ -CP	9	47	44	0.6	855.7 (2)	100	861.8	530.6 (b)

(*) reduction peak of NiO excess

(**) and (***) reduction peaks of Ni²⁺ in nickel aluminate

(1) Ni²⁺ as NiO and (2) Ni²⁺ as NiAl₂O₄.

(a) O²⁻ as NiO, (b) O²⁻ as NiAl₂O₄ and (c) O²⁻ as Al₂O₃

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Table 2

Reaction	Catalyst	H ₂ /CO			CO/CO ₂			Coke, % ⁽¹⁾
		450	550	650	450	550	650	
	Equilibrium	21.3	6.0	2.7	0.19	1.06	5.86	-
POM	NiAl ₂ O ₄ -D	5.5	3.5	2.2	0.24	0.57	3.00	46.5
	NiAl ₂ O ₄ -CP	12.7	4.4	2.5	0.10	0.60	3.00	2.5
	1%Rh/Al ₂ O ₃	2.5	2.8	2.4	0.74	1.29	3.46	2
	Equilibrium	44.9	11.9	6.7	0.10	0.45	1.09	-
SRM	NiAl ₂ O ₄ -D	118.6	19.2	8.5	0.05	0.34	1.03	<1
	NiAl ₂ O ₄ -CP	68.5	13.3	6.9	0.08	0.51	1.42	<1
	1%Rh/Al ₂ O ₃	19.7	12.6	8.2	0.31	0.56	1.06	<1
	Equilibrium	36.3	12.1	7.3	0.07	0.28	0.56	-
OSRM	NiAl ₂ O ₄ -D	43.1	20.1	10.3	0.05	0.16	0.39	<1
	NiAl ₂ O ₄ -CP	55.9	20.1	9.4	0.04	0.18	0.50	<1
	1%Rh/Al ₂ O ₃	8.9	10.8	7.8	0.14	0.31	0.65	<1

788 Reactions conditions: 38400 cm³ CH₄ g⁻¹ h⁻¹; W=0.125 g. Gas mixtures: POM: 10%CH₄/5%O₂/N₂, SRM: 10%CH₄/30%H₂O/N₂ and OSRM: 10%CH₄/30%H₂O/5%O₂/N₂.

789 ⁽¹⁾ Deposited carbon for used catalyst determined by TPO and TG analyses

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Table 3

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Fig. 1

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Fig. 2

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Fig. 3

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Fig. 4

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Fig. 5

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Fig. 6

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Fig. 7

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Fig. 8

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Fig. 9

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Fig. 10

Graphical abstract

ZTF-FCT
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HIGHLIGHTS – BULLET POINTS

Nickel aluminate catalysts were prepared by co-precipitation and co-dissolution.

The influence of the preparation method on the Ni distribution was discussed.

Well dispersed and homogeneous Ni was obtained on the co-precipitated NiAl_2O_4 .

This sample exhibited a high activity for various methane reforming reactions.

The catalytic behaviour was controlled by Ni particle size and surface acid density.